

Understanding misunderstanding: How quick-fix solutions undermine explanation

Laura van de Braak^{1,2}, Iris van Rooij^{1,2,3}, Mark Dingemans⁴, Ivan Toni², and Mark Blokpoel^{1,2}

¹Department of Cognitive Science and Artificial Intelligence,
Radboud University, The Netherlands

²Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition, and Behaviour,
Radboud University, The Netherlands

³Department of Linguistics, Cognitive Science, and Semiotics,
Aarhus University, Denmark

⁴Centre for Language Studies, Radboud University, The Netherlands

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Preface

This manuscript is a preprint of Chapter 4 in a doctoral dissertation submitted by Laura van de Braak at the Graduate School at the Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition, and Behaviour, titled ‘Understanding misunderstanding: A theoretical approach to explaining communicative alignment’. To make the manuscript self-contained the references to the other chapters in the thesis have been replaced with the relevant citations.

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Abstract

Communicative alignment is the capacity that, even when talking about novel things and without a fully shared vocabulary, people can come to understand each other. State-of-the-art models so far fail to provide a sufficient explanation for this phenomenon. When such models fail, researchers are often quick to suggest a solution to *quickly fix* the model and make it *work*. We propose a metatheoretical approach using four criteria to systematically assess explanatory

quality of computational explanations. We analyse the efficacy of different types of such suggested quick fixes following guidelines that a good computational explanation must be transparent, unambiguous, sufficient, and possible. Using these criteria we show that quick-fixes cannot be sufficient to achieve an explanation for communicative alignment. We show that even if there is a strong body of work on a topic, that does not guarantee such work is sufficient to quickly fix a computational model. It may be that a quick fix suggestion has the right idea, but often the methodology is under-specified or ill-formed. In some cases these quick fixes may even undermine finding explanations of communicative alignment, by obscuring the capacity or adding more theoretical problems to an existing explanation. We conclude it is not easy to fix an explanation for communicative alignment. With these analyses as starting point, we then classify the pitfalls within these different quick fixes in a meta-theoretic typology using maps as an analogy. It abstracts away from communicative alignment, and can thus be used to analyse possible quick-fixes in other domains.

1 Introduction

Communicative alignment is the capacity people have to come to mutual understanding, even when understanding is not yet shared. This capacity and the like have been subject of empirical and theoretical study for a long time (Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986; de Ruiter et al., 2007; Eijk et al., 2022; Galantucci & Garrod, 2011; Healey et al., 2018; Holler & Wilkin, 2011; Macuch Silva et al., 2020; Micklos et al., 2020; Nölle & Galantucci, 2022). In this paper, we show that communicative alignment seems to be particularly resistant to computational explanation.

Why take such a critical stance? Because, as cognitive scientists, our aim is to find explanations for cognitive capacities and improve our understanding of the world (Blokpoel & van Rooij, 2021; Cummins, 2000). We do not want to be led astray by focusing on making a model ‘work’ (c.f. van Rooij et al., 2024). We find explanations by developing theories according to strict computational criteria and applying critical reflection (Guest, 2024; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021; Woensdregt et al., 2024). While a critical stance is not guaranteed to lead to a proper explanation (Rich et al., 2021), the critical stance allows us to become aware of the limitations of our explanations. If we lose track of the aim, we may let ourselves be drawn into applying solutions to quickly make the model ‘work’ (e.g., assume shared understanding to have good simulation results). We call these solutions *quick-fixes*.

In this paper, we introduce a metatheoretic framework based on four computational criteria, and use them to critically reflect on models of communicative alignment proposed by van de Braak et al. (2021). These models were created to explain communicative alignment, but fail to fully do so in a few ways. We then apply meta-theoretic methodology (Guest, 2024; Guest & Martin, 2021) to identify and critically reflect on common quick-fixes to make these models ‘work’. We show that none of these quick-fixes will lead to a good explanation that is guaranteed to quickly satisfy all four of the criteria. The analysis of the quick-fixes highlights recurring patterns in the theoretical pitfalls these quick-fixes fall into, which we then create a typology from. This typology can be applied by computational cognitive scientists to perform similar theoretical analyses on different models in different domains.

In the rest of Section 4.1, we lay the groundwork to be able to critically analyse these quick-fixes. We introduce the phenomenon and model, as well as our criteria for a good explanation, and some further detail on why the non-ostensive model, for all its sophisticated reasoning, does

not ‘work’. In Section 4.2, we introduce several possible quick-fixes and analyse whether these fixes would have the intended effect. In Section 4.3, we summarise the results of Section 4.2, and provide intermediate conclusions. Next, Section 4.4 contains a metatheoretical typology to classify different types of quick-fixes, based on the analysis in Section 4.2. As these quick-fixes come from different sub-fields, this typology will be an aid to describing the perspective on fixes across cognitive science.

1.1 The Explanandum

In this section we describe the phenomenon *communicative alignment*, as we conceive it to be in the world. Communicative alignment is the cognitive capacity people have to come to mutual understanding in a situation where such understanding is not shared initially. Consider the following exchange (see also Figure 1) between you and a friend.

Your friend asks: “Could you pass me the dragon fruit?”.

You are unsure what they mean and inquire: “Do you mean the orange fruit in the bowl?”,
but they respond: “No, the pink one”.

Now you know which fruit they want, despite perhaps being uncertain what a dragon fruit was before.

This illustration shows people’s capacity to interactively come to mutual understanding (Clark & Schaefer, 1987; Dingemane, Roberts, et al., 2015; Micklos & Woensdregt, 2023; Schegloff et al., 1977), even in the absence of a (fully) shared vocabulary. This is the capacity for *communicative alignment* (van de Braak et al., 2021). Similarly to van de Braak et al. (2024),

[we] conceive of this capacity as something that people can do under minimal enabling conditions. For instance, these conditions include that both speakers commit to trying to reach mutual understanding and are engaging in good faith, [e.g., are cooperative

Figure 1: A platter of possibly unknown fruits, among which a dragon fruit. The other fruits on the platter include a mangosteen, a fig, a rambutan, a pineapple and a papaya. All fruits are shown as a whole fruit as well as cut in half.

(Grice, 1975; Levinson, 2006)]. If one of the actors violates these conditions (e.g., by engaging in ill-faith, deception (Dynel, 2020), or epistemic injustice (Pohlhaus, 2012)), then successful communicative alignment may be blocked. This does not mean that the capacity for communicative alignment is not real or robust, but it does need minimal conditions to operate properly. (van de Braak et al., 2024, p.1)

Communicative alignment has been studied extensively, both in natural conversation, e.g. through conversation analysis (Clift, 2016; Schegloff, 1991), and in experimental settings, e.g. through experimental semiotics (Galantucci & Garrod, 2011). Studies of natural conversation have identified several key behavioural properties. We highlight a few that are relevant to the phenomenon of communicative alignment. Firstly, interaction is turn-organised (Levinson, 2016; Sacks et al., 1974). Secondly, an integral element of turn-taking is methods to resolve trouble (Dingemanse & Enfield, 2024; Dingemanse, Roberts, et al., 2015; Schegloff et al., 1977). These repair methods to resolve trouble are “an interface between interaction and cognition” (Albert & de Ruiter, 2018, p302). Communication is fast: turns come at approximately 200ms after the previous utterance (Levinson, 2016; Micklos & Woensdregt, 2023; Roberts & Francis, 2013) and interactive repair facilitates rapid coordination and efficient communication (Dingemanse, Roberts, et al., 2015).

Complementary to conversation analysis, experimental studies can afford another lens on communicative alignment. We take inspiration from several experiments, such as the Tangrams (as introduced for behavioural experiments by Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986; Holler & Wilkin, 2011) and the Fribbles (Barry et al., 2014; Eijk et al., 2022; Rasenberg, Pouw, et al., 2022). See Figure 2 for an example of these objects. These Tangrams and Fribbles experiments afford representing novel referents, i.e., referents that (most likely) participants will have never seen or communicated about before (e.g., the dragon fruit in Figure 1). By challenging participants to reach mutual understanding over novel referential objects, misunderstandings and their resolutions are brought to the surface (as in Eijk et al., 2022; Micklos et al., 2020; Rasenberg, Özyürek, et al., 2022). This methodology corroborates the observations from conversation analysis (Schegloff et al., 1977; Seo & Koshik, 2010): they highlight that ostensive¹ signals are not necessary for communicative alignment (Eijk et al., 2022), and that communicative alignment can be multi-modal (Holler & Wilkin, 2011; Rasenberg, Özyürek, et al., 2022). Furthermore, the Tacit Communica-

Figure 2: Examples of novel objects used for experiments. Tangrams on the left, and Fribbles on the right

¹The term ostensive has two senses: (a) referential transparency, i.e., no (or little) reasoning is required to understand the meaning of the signal, or (b) a signal that communicates its own communicative value (Wilson & Sperber, 2004). Here, we use it in the first sense.

tion Game (Blokpoel et al., 2012; de Ruiter et al., 2007; de Weerd et al., 2015; Newman-Norlund et al., 2009; Stolk et al., 2013), like other experimental semiotic designs (de Ruiter et al., 2007; Galantucci & Garrod, 2011; Nölle & Galantucci, 2022; Ware, 1993), forces participants to communicate through a novel medium which illustrates that communicative alignment is language agnostic.

The phenomenon of communicative alignment, in the real world, is most likely even more complex, but the definition and properties we outlined serve as an important lower bound characterisation of that which we aim to explain.

1.2 The Explanatory Challenge

What does it mean to *explain* the explanandum? Here, we specifically seek to explain communicative alignment as a *cognitive capacity*. We adopt the following a definition of cognitive capacity, see also Cummins (2000) and van Rooij (2008):

"A capacity is a dispositional property of a system at one of its levels of organization: e.g., single neurons have capacities (firing, exciting, inhibiting) and so do minds and brains (vision, learning, reasoning) and groups of people (coordination, competition, polarization). A capacity is a more or less reliable ability (or disposition or tendency) to transform some initial state (or 'input') into a resulting state ('output')." (van Rooij & Baggio, 2021, p3.)

Communicative alignment, put in these terms, is a capacity at the level of organisation of multiple people (specifically, more than one), and is a type of coordination (communicative coordination). As such, it is an interactional cognitive capacity. It is the more or less reliable ability for people to (interactively) transform a state of no mutual understanding (on some topic or object) into a state of mutual understanding.

Communicative alignment is an interactional capacity because it takes place at the level of organisation of at least two people. There is inherently an interactional component to the capacity. The capacity is defined as to reach a state of shared understanding. This must thus occur between at least two people for any understanding to be able to be shared. It is also a cognitive capacity, in that it requires cognitive components – at the single person level – that facilitate this interactional aspect.²

Cognitive capacities can be explained at different levels of analysis. Throughout this paper, we focus on explaining communicative alignment at the *computational* level (Marr, 1982),³ also known as *function-theoretic* explanation (Egan, 2017): "A computational-level theory of a ca-

²If one does not want to commit to the possibility of shared cognitive capacities, the individual cognitive capacity is still one that can only operate in interaction. If one believes cognition cannot be at group level, then this whole phenomenon and any other that is in interaction falls outside cognitive science. In our approach we take theorising about the higher level of organisation serious (see also de Jaegher et al., 2010; Dingemanse et al., 2023; Enfield, 2013; Fusaroli et al., 2014; Gentner, 2019; Mercier & Sperber, 2018; Wheatley et al., 2019). Whether or not one calls that cognitive is perhaps not even relevant.

³Other levels usually distinguished include the algorithmic level and implementational level (Marr, 1982) (see also van Rooij and Blokpoel (2020) for a tutorial explanation of the levels). These types of explanations, while useful for cognitive science generally, are outside the scope of this paper.

capacity is a specification of input states, I , and output states, O , and the theorised mapping, $f : I \rightarrow O$.” (van Rooij & Baggio, 2021, p. 3).

Explaining communicative alignment qua capacity minimally requires a theoretical formal account how a cogniser can reliably transition from a given cognitive state (misunderstanding) to another cognitive state (understanding) that is minimally *transparent* (Guest & Martin, 2021; van Rooij, 2022), *unambiguous* (Guest & Martin, 2021), *sufficient* (Blokpoel, 2018) and *possible* (van Rooij & Baggio, 2021). We can use these four properties for a systematic metatheoretical analysis of computational explanations of (interactional) cognitive capacities.

To illustrate the necessity of these four criteria, let us consider an example of a very simple interactional cognitive capacity: to guess a number k between, say, 1 and $n \geq k$, that someone else has in mind⁴. Here, the interactional cognitive capacity is to transition from a state where only one of the agents knows this number k , to a state where both agents know the number. While this is a very simple cognitive capacity in terms of the scope of the things to communicate about (numbers only, in a game with simple rules), it is still an interactional capacity.

Take a moment to think about how this may go. How would you guess a number that someone else holds in their mind? You probably have ideas about how you would go about this, and maybe they are even true. However, as long as you do not make transparent your ideas of how this works, for instance, by verbalising and/or writing them down, they remain inaccessible for other theoreticians to understand and assess. Hence, step 1 is to articulate your ideas about what each agent contributes cognitively to this interactional capacity. Let us start to do so, informally.

(Informal sketch) The initial, or ‘starting’, state is that the first agent (let us call them the ‘knower’) is given a number k . The other agent (let us call them the ‘guesser’) can, say, guess a number. In turn, the knower has three response options, ‘yes’ (if the number is correct) and otherwise ‘higher’ or ‘lower’.

While this informal sketch makes explicit ones idea of how coordination may be achieved in this guessing game, and is in that sense made *transparent*, it does not yet meet the conditions of *unambiguity*. For instance, what numbers can the guesser all guess? This is still ambiguous. For instance, what kind of numbers? Are the numbers real or integer or rational or irrational? Are they positive only, or are negative numbers also allowed? We also need to spell out under which conditions exactly the knower will say ‘higher’ or ‘lower’. While this may seem intuitively obvious, a *transparent* and *unambiguous* computational explanation needs to make all of this explicit.

Let us try.

INITIAL-KNOWER (VERSION 1)

Input: The number $k \in \mathcal{C}$, where $\mathcal{C} \in \{\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}^+, \mathbb{C}, \dots\}$ and a range $[k_{min}, k_{max}]$.

Output: “I have a number!”

⁴We made this game up for the purpose of this paper, but more of such coordination games exist (Cooper et al., 1992; Cooper, 1999; Schelling, 1958; Van Huyck et al., 1990)

GUESSER (VERSION 1)

Input: All previously guessed numbers, and the connected responses from the knower (in the first round this list will be empty).

Output: A guess g consistent with the information so far.

KNOWER (VERSION 1)

Input: k and guess g

Output: a response: $\begin{cases} \text{'indeed'} & \text{if } g = k \\ \text{'lower'} & \text{if } g > k \\ \text{'higher'} & \text{if } g < k \end{cases}$

Let's see what happens when we simulate these models for a given input for the INITIAL-KNOWER. The guesser first guesses 7, and the knower answers 'higher'. Then the guesser guesses 8, and again the knower answers 'higher'. This continues, back and forth for a while, and you now realise that the range is unknown to guesser (and the reader; maybe you had by default assumed it was $[1,10]$). We also now realise that our model was incomplete (or *insufficient*), as we originally stated "To illustrate, let us consider an example of a very simple cognitive capacity: to guess a number k between, say, 1 and $n \geq k$, that someone else has in mind.". Hence, we need to update and correct the model:

INITIAL-KNOWER (VERSION 2)

Input: The number $k \in \mathcal{C}$, where $\mathcal{C} \in \{\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}^+, \mathbb{C}, \dots\}$ and a range $[k_{min}, k_{max}]$.

Output: "I have a number between k_{min} and k_{max} !"

GUESSER (VERSION 2)

Input: The k_{min} and k_{max} shared by the Knower, all previously guessed numbers, and the connected responses from the knower (in the first round this list will be empty).

Output: A guess g consistent with the information so far.

Let us continue the example guessing. The guesser guesses 878, and the knower answers again 'higher'. Then the guesser guesses 879, and the knower answers 'lower'. Now we realise that the number k is not an integer, but could be real or rational. Let us say the number is a real number. Then within an ostensibly finite range there exist an infinite number of possibilities. Hence, the models we proposed would not be *possible* or *sufficient*.

They cannot be *possible* because the knower and guesser from the model can get into an infinite loop. If the number has to be higher than 878 and lower than 879, it is possible that every round a decimal number just gets added to result in $878.99999999\dots$, which may never reach an end. We do not have the capacity for guessing reals (cf. van Rooij & Baggio, 2021), so that should also not be present in the models.

These models are also not *sufficient*. If the boundaries of what type of number are not clear, the agents may not ever reach a successful ending to the game. As in the original capacity playing

the game will always result in a successful ending (if one remembers all statements and guesses accordingly), this model as such is thus not a *sufficient* model to explain the capacity.

Hence, to ensure both *sufficiency* and *possibility* the type of number allowed needs to be restricted and communicated. It needs to be restricted so that the resulting model will be *possible*, and the restriction needs to be communicated so the resulting model will be *sufficient*.

So to conclude, a model of a guessing game that has all properties *transparent*, *unambiguous*, *sufficient* and *possible* could be the following:

INITIAL-KNOWER (VERSION 3)

Input: The number $k \in \mathcal{C}$, where $\mathcal{C} \in \{\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{Z}\}$ and a range $[k_{min}, k_{max}]$ where $k_{min}, k_{max} \in \mathcal{C}$.

Output: "I have a number between k_{min} and k_{max} with $k \in \mathcal{C}$!"

GUESSER (VERSION 3)

Input: The k_{min} and k_{max} shared by the Knower, all previously guessed numbers, as well as the connected responses from the knower (in the first round this list will be empty).

Output: A guess $g \in \mathcal{C}$ that is $k_{min} < g < k_{max}$, higher than any previous guess that got the response "higher", and lower than any previous guess that got the response "lower".

KNOWER (VERSION 3)

Input: k and guess g

Output: a response: $\begin{cases} \text{'indeed'} & \text{if } g = k \\ \text{'lower'} & \text{if } g > k \\ \text{'higher'} & \text{if } g < k \end{cases}$

Let's see how a concrete situation could unfold: The Knower proclaims 'I have a number between 0 and 20!'. The Guesser replies, '17?' The Knower responds 'lower'. The Guesser replies '12'. The Knower responds 'higher'. The Guesser replies '14'. The Knower responds 'lower'. Guesser: '13!'. Knower: 'indeed!'.

While the computational-level models are consistent with this sequence of turns, it does not explain how the Guesser chooses their particular guesses and not others. When people play these kinds of guessing games, they display all kinds of strategic biases in their guesses (Bonanno, 2015; de Weerd et al., 2015; Schelling, 1961; Van Benthem et al., 2015). These computational level models do not (yet) incorporate explanations of those strategies. For instance, the first guess '17' could be motivated by the pragmatics of the Knower saying that their number is between 0 and 20 (because if the number were below 10, then they could have said between 0 and 10; assuming they are cooperative. Subsequently, the guess '14' seems motivated by the strategy of binary search (i.e., a search algorithm that operates by halving the search space; Knuth (1968)). By incorporating these strategies in the models, the models could be made even more realistic and explanatory. Be that as it may, the simple models as stated are already *sufficient* to explain the core capacity of people to be (minimally) able to guess a number held in mind by another person, even if it does not explain details of patterns of this guessing. This illustrates that (incomplete)

models can be explanatorily sufficient for some explananda while explanatorily insufficient for other explananda. In other words, sufficiency is dependent on what the exact explanandum is considered to be. In this case, the capacity for guessing numbers at all, or guessing them in particular ways.

We use this example to illustrate our minimal standards we set for computational-level explanations for the cognitive capacity of communicative alignment. In other words, for communicative alignment we seek a computational explanation that is *transparent, unambiguous, sufficient* and *possible*, just as the computational-level explanation given here for our Number Guessing capacity.

To further emphasise the point, we next compare the explanatory challenge for communicative alignment with the (simple) number guessing game, and analyse which simplifying conditions render the number guessing game much harder to explain than the communicative alignment (and both of them harder to explain than non-interactional capacities). Table 1 gives an overview of these conditions.

First of all, in the guessing game there is a 1:1 mapping between referents and signals, such that the conversation partners do *not need to engage in any complex inferences* to understand which referent the other is referring to: i.e., if the guesser says ‘7’ then the knower knows exactly which number is referred to, namely ‘7’. In contrast, in everyday communicative alignment this condition is not always met; see e.g., the fruit bowl example in Figure 1. It is even definitional of the capacity of communicative alignment that the referent of a signal is initially unclear (see Section 1.1).

Second, in the guessing game there is no ambiguity within an agent’s lexicon: e.g., a ‘7’ means just ‘7’ and not also sometimes ‘6’, ‘8’ or ‘a cow’. In contrast, in everyday communication ambiguity is widespread, e.g., we may refer to objects by some of their features possibly shared with other objects. See e.g. the earlier fruit bowl example in Figure 1; but the same applies if we use ‘the table’ to refer to the kitchen table and not the dining room or side table. In everyday conversation these ambiguities are resolved through pragmatic inferences (i.e., taking into account which objects are all in view and what other things a speaker *could* have said about the referent but didn’t (see also conversational implicature; Levinson (2000))).

Third, in the guessing game the lexica of the two players are identical. That is, at least in version

	NUMBER GUESSING	COMMUNICATIVE ALIGNMENT
inference needed	No	Yes
ambiguity within lexicon	No	Yes
asymmetric lexicon between agents	No	Yes
non-reducible search space	No	Yes
interaction needed to resolve	Yes	Yes

Table 1: A table showing the difference of several properties of NUMBER GUESSING versus COMMUNICATIVE ALIGNMENT. This illustrates how many different components of an interactional cognitive capacity are made easy for NUMBER GUESSING. In contrast, in COMMUNICATIVE ALIGNMENT all these components need to be accounted for in the explanation.

3.⁵ We saw that in the earlier versions this condition was not the case, because the domain of numbers was unspecified by the Knower. This caused problems when trying to model/explain how the Guesser could correctly guess numbers that the Knower could have in mind. Now imagine the extra complexity added to the explanatory challenge when asymmetry between lexica of agents is a property of the explanandum, as is the case for communicative alignment. After all, in everyday communicative alignment people need not initially share the same lexicon (see again, the fruit bowl example) but nevertheless through interaction can come to understand the referent meant by a speaker correctly.

Fourth, assuming a finite⁶ domain, in the guessing game there is a guaranteed search space reduction with every back-and-forth interaction step. For instance, if the Knower says ‘I have a number between 1 and 10’, and the Guesser guesses ‘7’, and Knower replies ‘higher’, then the Guesser can be certain that the correct number is ‘not 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, nor 7’. In contrast, because of the potential ambiguity and asymmetry inherent in communicative alignment the (size of) search space for possible referents given a history of interaction and speech acts may remain unchanged and all ambiguity and asymmetry may need to be resolved via pragmatic inferences, not simply by elimination.

Lastly, both the number guessing game and communicative alignment are so-called interactional cognitive capacities. That is, they cannot be reduced to an individual’s cognition, but instead are situated and distributed over a pair of conversation partners (Dingemanse et al., 2023; Levinson, 2006). While they both share this feature, in scientific practice we see a predominant focus on capacities studied in single-person/agent situations. In an interactional cognitive capacity, there are more elements of a situation that play a role in how the capacity works. Further, the elements are not completely independent of each other but rather dependent and interwoven. It is not possible to explain separate components of the capacity and then tie those components together to have a full explanation. All the components being dependent and interwoven means that the only way to explain the capacity is to explain the entire capacity. This complicates the modelling process.

This analysis of the number guessing game illustrates how complex it is to make a model that is *transparent, unambiguous, sufficient* and *possible* even for a seemingly trivial example capacity. Communicative alignment is an especially complex and difficult capacity to explain. All the above named properties are present in *communicative alignment*. Hence, in creating a model of the capacity, we need not just concern ourselves with transparency, unambiguity, sufficiency and possibility, but also complex inference, lexicon ambiguity and asymmetry, a non-decreasing search space, as well as interaction. We now turn to a candidate model that sets out to meet the explanatory challenge.

1.3 The Explanation

To address the challenge posed in the previous section, van de Braak et al. (2021) created two models that are based on the Rational Speech Act framework (Frank & Goodman, 2012; Hawkins et al., 2017). At a conceptual level, the Rational Speech Act (RSA) framework assumes that all interlocutors in a conversation rationally deduce what the most likely referent is, given a

⁵In versions 1 and 2 there is still a large overlap between the lexica, as they both concern numbers, but the differing classes of numbers mean that they cannot be considered identical.

⁶For infinite space this does not work.

communicated signal, or what the best signal is if the intention is a specific referent. This pragmatic inference is theoretically grounded in Blokpoel et al. (2011), Grice (1975), and van Rooij et al. (2011)’s rational reasoning concepts.

The Hawkins et al. (2017) model is a model of convention-formation, based on an empirical experiment reported on in the same paper. These researchers define conventions as “arbitrary but stable solutions to recurring coordination problems” (Hawkins et al., 2017, p.1). Importantly, this is a different capacity than communicative alignment.

Convention formation as in Hawkins et al. (2017) is focused on finding an arbitrary but stable *convention* in a situation with no starting conventions defined. The convention-formation model is a one-shot interaction where a signal is communicated and the referent is deduced. It summarises the convention-formation process and captures just the initial communication of an interaction where the director’s communicates their intention, and the matcher’s final response. Communicative alignment is the capacity for coming to mutual understanding in conversation.

To adapt the convention formation model into a model of communicative alignment, there are two large adaptations made by van de Braak et al. (2021). The two resulting models can be seen in their *transparent* and *unambiguous* state in the appendix of van de Braak et al. (2024). For this paper it is not necessary to understand all model details, so the formal models are not repeated here.

The first of these changes resulted in the Ostensive model and are related to *interaction*. The relevance of interaction for understanding cognition has long been recognised in work on distributed cognition. (Hutchins, 2006) and language as joint action (Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986). Their main point is that rather than studying the function of a single mind, it is possible and valuable to study how minds interact with each other (see also Dingemans et al., 2023). Because in communication people tend to converse with one another rather than just talk at someone, this is an essential point of view to incorporate. We also introduced this concept in Section 1.2. In an interactional model both agents in a conversation can communicate back and forth until they reach their intended goal (in this case: to successfully resolve a misunderstanding and reach mutual understanding).

The second model is the non-ostensive model. In the convention-formation model (Hawkins et al., 2017), as well as in many other models of communication in the field (such as Steels,

Figure 3: *Ostensive Communication.* The pair on the left shows agents communicating. The pair on the right shows the initiating agent literally placing the intended referent into the head of the other agent. This literal placement of an object into an interlocutor’s head is not possible in natural communication.

2015), the receiving agent can use what is known as ‘ostensive signalling’ or ‘explicit feedback’ to unambiguously indicate what their interpretation of the signal was, to allow for common ground to be learned. We liken this to being able to directly place the intended referent into the other agent’s head (see Figure 3). In effect what this does is give the model the information to unambiguously converge on the signal-meaning mappings that the receiver possesses. So rather than the convergence of models being an indication of what was learned through the interaction, the convergence merely indicates what convergence is possible if the conversation is unambiguously grounded in one of the interlocutors and the other party will just accept this as truth. This is not how we have characterised the capacity of communicative alignment. Furthermore, it is something that is not always possible in human communication, and thus not necessary to incorporate in our models.

The non-ostensive model inherits the interactional capacity from the Ostensive model. However, that ability to explicitly point at a referent to resolve the misunderstanding is removed. Instead both agents are supplied with additional reasoning capabilities (made up of additional pragmatic inferences) to be able to resolve the misunderstanding through words alone. This assumption is quite reasonable, as empirical research shows that people do reach mutual understanding on novel objects such as the Tangrams (Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986; Elffers & Hollingdale, 1976; Holler & Wilkin, 2011) or the Fribbles (Barry et al., 2014), see also Figure 2). Furthermore, it is not always possible or feasible to explicitly point to an intended referent, e.g. when talking about an object not currently in the same room (Galati & Brennan, 2021; Hockett, 1960), or even when talking about abstract concepts such as ‘how to explain communicative alignment’.

The developments of replacing ostensive signalling with more pragmatic reasoning, added to the interactional components of the ostensive model, make the non-ostensive model a decent candidate for an explanation of communicative alignment. However, as we explain next, results from simulations of this model indicate otherwise.

1.4 Why it fails

Simulations based on above-mentioned models show that unexamined assumptions of ostension obscure explanations of how people come to mutual understanding. We give a brief overview here, for full details, see results in van de Braak et al. (2021).

In the model, agents end an interaction when they perceive mutual understanding to be reached (perceived understanding). Initial analysis of the simulation results showed that agents indeed seemed to reach understanding over time. Further, the number of turns of interaction necessary to reach such understanding decreased over time. This seemed to align with existing literature on interactive repair early in referential communication tasks (Degen et al., 2019; Hawkins et al., 2017; Mills, 2014). Further analysis showed that the ostensive model was achieving factual understanding (defined as agents aligning on the same referent after the final interaction) frequently and was achieving this early in the interactions. However, the non-ostensive model showed very low factual understanding in general, and also needed more interactions to get there. We continued the analysis, the results of which are re-printed in Table 2. This table shows that while the non-ostensive agents were reaching perceived understanding at similar rates as the ostensive agents, the non-ostensive agents are not reaching factual understanding. Rather, given that the simulations were run over a lexicon size of 4 signals and 3 referents, the non-ostensive agents are near chance level for guessing a correct referent. In contrast, the ostensive agents *do* manage to

Table 2: Percentage of simulated dialogues that end in factual understanding split by whether the agents perceived understanding or gave up the interaction (after 7 turns). Chance level for factual understanding is 34.3%. Table reprinted from van de Braak et al. (2021)

	perceived understanding	give up
ostensive	79.5 %	42.0 %
non-ostensive	34.4 %	33.4 %

reach mutual factual understanding.

The simulation results show that while the non-ostensive agents believe to be getting closer to mutual understanding, and believe to reach that, the final referents they have in mind objectively do not match up to each other. Even though agents have a high perceived understanding, their factual mutual understanding is around chance level. The agents cannot understand each other, even in an interaction. Clearly, the model provides no explanation for the capacity for communicative alignment. Just as clearly, people do have this capacity (Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986; de Ruiter et al., 2007; Eijk et al., 2022; Galantucci & Garrod, 2011; Holler & Wilkin, 2011), so we know that there is a severe gap in the explanation initially given for this phenomenon.

This gap between perceived mutual understanding and factual mutual understanding has not been noted before in similar lines of research, as many models assume that ostensive signalling will be available to resolve any gaps in communication. The conclusion reached by van de Braak et al. (2021) was that “[w]ithout referentially clear signals, non-ostensive agents have no way of knowing when their inferences are factually correct” (van de Braak et al., 2021, p.6). And that: “computational theories of communication need to be expanded with a different kind of reasoning, one that explains how people can use context, background knowledge and other semiotic resources (Clark, 2006; Clark, 1997) to attain sufficient meta-understanding” (van de Braak et al., 2021, p.6).

There are two other main theoretical problems that we found within these models. Firstly, the non-ostensive and the ostensive model are both intractable (van de Braak et al., 2024). Through computational complexity analysis it was found that both model variants are intractable. Furthermore, this intractability holds for several model variants and is robust for many parameters. This means it is not possible to make a simple change to the model and expect the intractability to just be resolved; it is inherent to all the sophisticated reasoning between agents present in the model. An intractable model cannot yield a good explanation for cognition as by the Tractable Cognition Thesis, any cognitive model needs to be tractable to be at minimum plausible to be an explanation for a cognitive capacity (van Rooij, 2008). Thus, following our criteria, an intractable model does not meet the criterion of *possibility*.

Secondly, the ostensive model is built on a ‘cognitive scope violation’, as defined in Adolphi et al. (2024): “[a] theory violates a *cognitive scope* constraint when it incorporates an assumption that is at odds with the real-world generality of the cognitive capacity studied” (Adolphi et al., 2024, p. 5). Communicative alignment, as we defined earlier, is people’s capacity to interactively come to mutual understanding, even in the initial absence of such mutual understanding. We see in e.g. the Fribbles and Tangram experiments (Clark & Wilkes-Gibbs, 1986; Eijk et al., 2022; Elffers & Hollingdale, 1976; Holler & Wilkin, 2011; Rasenberg, Pouw, et al., 2022) that this capacity is present even when it is not possible for people to provide explicit unambiguous feedback on

what the intended meaning was that is being referred to. As such, any model of this capacity should thus also be able to explain this. This capacity for reaching mutual understanding without access to explicit unambiguous feedback is ambiguously present in Hawkins et al. (2017). In the empirical experiments in that paper, people can resolve misunderstandings through language (if text-based language only), only receiving feedback after perceived understanding has been reached. Yet, in their computational model, this resolution process has been removed and replaced with direct explicit feedback. Thus, the ostensive model cannot be a good explanation for communicative alignment as it only captures a slice of the capacity rather than the whole of it. The ostensive model can thus not be a *sufficient* explanation for communicative alignment as it does not explain the whole of the capacity.

1.5 What comes next?

In the ostensive model the back and forth interaction paradigm was added by van de Braak et al. (2021) to better capture the process of a resolution of misunderstanding. However, the responder is able to ostensively signal, without ambiguity, which referent it had inferred. While the signal they speak to resolve the misunderstanding is also included, the resolution process can thus always rely on the unambiguous ostensive signal for their understanding. This is implausible and an undergeneralisation (cf. van Rooij, 2015) to the cognitive capacity, as we stated above. Thus, in the continuation of this paper, we will focus on the non-ostensive model, as it does not suffer from this undergeneralisation. If we would continue with the ostensive model, we risk being blinded by the illusion of successful communicative alignment, thus allowing it to undermine our explanation, where in fact it inherently cannot explain the capacity. As the above analysis shows, there are several problems with the non-ostensive model, and yet it is the closest state-of-the-art model of communicative alignment. So what comes next?

There are several options. First, one could choose to do the slow work and theoretically develop a computational change to the model. This would then be followed by analysis of the new model, to determine whether it proves a better explanation for the capacity. Second, one could choose to ignore all that possible hard work and attempt to just quickly fix the model to make it ‘work’. Finally, one could create a third option and instead write a long theoretical treatise analysing several of these possible quick-fix suggestions as well as the impact such quick-fixes have on the theoretical landscape. Given the title and length of this paper, it should be clear which one the authors chose for this paper.

One might ask why one of the options mentioned for what comes next is not to bin the entire model and start from scratch if it performs so poorly on the capacity, especially also given the added intractability of the model. The problems named indicate that the current explanation is neither *possible* nor *sufficient*. Our answer to that is multi-faceted. Firstly, we believe that it is not good scientific practice to toss out an entire theory just because part of it does not explain as intended (cf. van Rooij et al., 2019, who make this point regarding intractability). Secondly, it is only through understanding our misunderstanding of a topic that we can learn how to better understand. Throwing out a model without a critical reflection of *why* it does not work means it is not possible to learn and understand what elements caused it to not work. Hence, by trying to make this theory ‘work’ we learn important things about the limits of our field’s scientific understanding of the phenomenon.

In this paper we evaluate suggested solutions (quick-fixes) to gain an understanding of whether

the suggested quick-fix will make an explanatory difference to our theory. We mentioned in Section 1.2 what, to us, makes a good explanation. We use the standards mentioned there to analyse the quick-fixes for their efficacy as adding to good explanation.

2 Quick-fixes

Based on the results of the non-ostensive model as developed by van de Braak et al. (2021), we received several comments from the field. At first, the comments inspired reflections on the model, but then also on the nature of those comments. Where there were disagreements with our conclusions, many seemed to think that a ‘faulty’ model (such as ours) could and should be ‘fixed’; be *made* to work⁷. This occasionally also came in the form of suggestions how to quickly fix the model. Here we will use the metatheoretical framework introduced in Section 4.1.2 to critically analyse these quick-fix suggestions. Are they truly *quick*? Will they even *fix*? Do they cause more theoretical problems by being *impossible*? Will they result in a model that can *sufficiently* explain? Do they increase our understanding of communicative alignment or do they only serve to obscure explanation?

In this section we perform a theoretical analysis for five of these possible quick-fixes, which come from a variety of sources. These quick-fixes are inspired by fields of literature adjacent to communicative alignment or to computational cognitive modelling. Many of these sources stem from personal communication but where they align or resonate with existing ideas in the literature we refer to them.

We consider all quick-fixes from a computationalist perspective, analysing them using the criteria for good computational explanations as introduced in Section 1.2: *transparency*, *unambiguity*, *sufficiency*, and *possibility*. All of the quick-fixes, in their original framing, are suggestions that do not yet incorporate any steps towards a formal description. To engage with all the quick-fixes in good faith, we show some of possible initial steps in coming to a formal description. We do this through a dialogical or question-based approach, as shown in Section 1.2 and as inspired by van Rooij and Blokpoel (2020).

All quick-fixes will be assumed to be suggestions of what to *quickly* add on to the non-ostensive model to *fix* it. For the model to be fixed, it needs to be able to explain the capacity for communicative alignment *in full*. In the analysis, we therefore take the quick-fixes seriously to reveal their explanatory limitations in the computational framework.

2.1 Add context and/or background knowledge

Suggested quick-fix: Of course the agents cannot communicate successfully without context or background knowledge, so you should just those to the model. Then it will work.

This is one of the most commonly suggested responses in the view of our previous results. Indeed, we ourselves stated this as prospective future work at the end of our 2021 paper (van de Braak et al., 2021).

⁷See also makeism (van Rooij et al., 2024), and success-to-truth inference (Guest & Martin, 2023)

People use context in conversation, and have background knowledge available that helps inform us how to respond in a situation (Clark, 1996; Clark & Brennan, 1991). People can also apply that contextual knowledge to help achieve communicative alignment. The model does not use context in such a way to ground any of the referents. If it is such a widely used attribute of language, then why is it listed here as an attempt at a quick-fix? To answer this question, we analyse this quick-fix as a specific suggestion to alter the existing non-ostensive model introduced in 1.2 in such a way as to reach communicative alignment through the addition of context and background knowledge to the model.

Of course, the main question is *how* to add the context. In computational cognitive modelling we ask “what is the nature of the problem solved by the capacity?” (Blokpoel & van Rooij, 2021; van de Braak et al., 2021) to make a description of a (cognitive) capacity. In the case studied in the current paper, that becomes: “what is the nature of the problem solved by communicative alignment?”. To incorporate context, we thus need to describe what context adds to the existing description.

To do that, however, it is necessary to be specific about what needs to be added, and those specificities are not mentioned in the quick-fix solution. This is part of why we call such suggestions a *quick-fix*; it is quick to suggest something like this if you need not be specific. This specificity is necessary to describe a model in a way that is both *transparent* and *unambiguous*. To achieve this, we need to go through the formal modelling process, for example by asking many questions to capture the changes to the model (Blokpoel, 2018; van Rooij & Blokpoel, 2020).

Let us illustrate some of the questions we would need to answer were we to incorporate context into the non-ostensive model. What does ‘context’ or ‘background knowledge’ look like? Is it extra knowledge? If so, how is it represented? How can this representation interact with the existing framework of the non-ostensive model?

This and many other similar questions would need to be answered to reach a description of a computational theory that could be seen as a specific computational suggestion to the model. For such a broad concept as context, it truly is necessary to ask and answer all these questions specifically (read: formally), as there are no clear computational accounts at present.

After all this has been done, that leaves us with a second question: will this quick-fix actually *fix* what it is intended to fix?

This question would seem very hard to answer without doing the modelling and then studying the resulting model. However, while it is hard to prove whether something will definitely fix without doing the modelling work, it is possible to analyse the prospective changes to the model. For example, it may be possible to determine that a model is *insufficient* or *impossible* purely based on theoretical analysis (cf. Guest & Martin, 2023; van Rooij, 2008; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021).

A concern that arises when looking at this quick-fix is the size of the search space in the model. The non-ostensive model is already proven to be intractable, as is the simpler ostensive model (van de Braak et al., 2024). Adding all extra information needed to reason with context can potentially exacerbate the problem of intractability, or at the very least will not resolve it. More information is not always better when the theory ends up being computationally *impossible*.

This conclusion runs counter to the intuition that computational *impossibility* is resolved when the model need not consider all of the knowledge added to add context, but only the relevant part

(Sperber & Wilson, 2001; Wilson & Sperber, 2004). Unfortunately, this raises another concern, known as the (cognitive) frame problem (Fodor, 2001). For a full description, see Box 1. The short version is as follows:

To select only the relevant elements from the full collection of knowledge is difficult. To select only the relevant part it is always necessary to consider the entire set. If we need to consider the entire collection of knowledge to determine the relevant part, we end up considering the entire collection rather than just the relevant part. Thus, unless the frame problem can be resolved, this is not a solution for this quick-fix. As such, we can already determine that the quick-fix will not be *possible*.

Box 1: *The Frame Problem*

An initial definition of the frame problem was coined (McCarthy & Hayes, 1969) within the domain of logic-based reasoning. Later came broader interpretations, applying it to the wider domain of cognitive science and AI (work by Fodor (1983) and Morgenstern (1996) among others). In this interpretation, the frame problem is the problem of explaining how a cognitive system (such as a person or a cognitive model) can determine a “frame” that includes the useful or relevant set of information from within the collection of *all* the available information.

Research (such as Sperber and Wilson (2001)) that claims people can take the *relevant* information thus need to account for how to deal with the frame problem. While it may be possible to determine the relevant frame given all available information, this runs the risk of tractability concerns for always needing to consider all possible information just to determine the relevant frame.

To conclude, this quick-fix suggests to ‘just add context to the model’. In the above analysis we show that this cannot be *quick*, as the steps that need to be taken to make this suggestion *transparent* and *unambiguous* take time to do properly. The many open questions regarding computational characterisation of context impede integration into the model. While we cannot determine whether this quick-fix would yield a model that provides a *sufficient* explanation, neither have we found any problems that would indicate insufficiency. For that, formal modelling and more analysis would need to be performed. Further, we argue that there is no guarantee for this to *fix* the model as new theoretical issues will be introduced that may render the model *impossible*. Specifically we mention relevance and the frame problem, that may—for the foreseeable future (cf. van Rooij et al., 2024) or forever (cf. Fodor, 2001), depending on who you ask—defy computational explanation.

2.2 Add iconicity

Suggested quick-fix: You should just add iconicity to the model, because people also use iconicity to help with communicative alignment. Then it will work.

The notion of iconicity has been described in various manners. For example, Perniss et al. (2010, p.2) characterise iconicity as “regular correspondences between form and meaning across both spoken and signed language modalities, motivated by perceptuo-motor properties of real-world experiences”. Similarly, Dingemanse, Blasi, et al. (2015, p.604) characterise iconicity as “the resemblance-based mapping between aspects of form and meaning” and Winter et al. (n.d.,

p.3) as “[a] signal in any modality or medium exhibits iconicity when its production and/or interpretation involves a sense of resemblance between at least some aspect of its form and at least some aspect of its meaning.”

These characterisations of iconicity all propose that in an iconic mapping between a signal (word) and its referent (meaning), some properties of the signal resemble the referent in some way and vice versa (Punselie et al., 2024). These relations exist along different modalities of language, being present in both spoken and signed languages, as well as being present in co-speech gestures (Perniss & Vigliocco, 2014). It is thought that iconicity can aid in word learning and language processing (Nielsen & Dingemanse, 2021; Perniss & Vigliocco, 2014), and thus enhances comprehension in communication.

People who suggest this quick-fix may believe that adding iconicity to the model will help agents reach communicative alignment. To *computationally* explain iconicity (or to use iconicity in a computational explanation), we must assume that cognition has access to these aspects of form and meaning.

As we see it, there are at least two different ways this quick-fix could be approached. The first is at a within-model level, in which we stay close to the non-ostensive model: iconicity means that for some signals there is less ambiguity over interpretation. The second is that these aspects of form and meaning are represented and present throughout the whole model, and as such it is necessary to build a model of communication on such a representation. As there are two ways this quick-fix can be interpreted, we will discuss both of these in turn.

Firstly, within-model, which we interpret as making changes in a way that stays close to the existing model. If we oversimplify “the resemblance-based mapping between aspects of form and meaning” (Dingemanse, Blasi, et al., 2015, p.604) to closely fit with the existing model, we could state there are several signal-referent mappings within a lexicon that are iconic, and thus less likely to be misinterpreted. One way this could be translated to the non-ostensive model is to ground specific signal-referent mappings as truth, and only consider lexica that have a positive match for this mapping.

Because of its resemblance-based relation between signals and referents, iconic signal-referent mappings are more likely to be shared along a larger group of people, even between different cultures or languages. However, while iconic signal-referent mappings may be shared more than some other mappings, this does not exclude other mappings being made to that signal or even that referent. To express this in terms of the model: an iconic signal-referent mapping will mean that all lexica in which that signal-referent mapping is not present will have probability 0. This will hold for both agents.

That the lexica without this mapping receive probability 0 in the lexical bias can be explained as follows. If an iconic signal holds stronger than other signals, this signal will be more likely to be available and present. An analogue of this in our models is that all possible lexica have this mapping present. It is still possible that there are also other mappings available for that signal and referent, but by being present in all available lexica, the iconic signal-referent mapping is more prevalent than the rest.

This would be a relatively quick change to the model, and these are changes that could be made *transparent* and *unambiguous*. Would such a change to the model *fix* the current problems of the model? Conceptually, a change on a within-model level means determining some elements as ground truth. This may indeed lead to a higher perceived understanding, as the iconic signals

will be interpreted the same by both agents. While this will lead to reduction of ambiguity and improving of some of the results, the main question is: will it be enough? In communicative alignment agents can reach shared mutual understanding through communication. In this definition we do not limit the shared understanding to only iconic signals. The result of this quick-fix would only improve the result for iconic signals and not for the non-iconic signals. Recall that the requirement for ‘fixing’ is to explain the capacity for communicative alignment in full. Hence, the within-model iconicity quick-fix is not *sufficient* to provide a good computational explanation.

Finally, we look at whether this quick-fix can be *possible*. As it remains close to the non-ostensive model, it likely inherits the intractability from that. It could be argued that the intractability is not made worse by these changes, however, that does not mean any existing intractability is resolved.

To conclude, while this within-model iconicity quick-fix may be quick to make *transparent* and *unambiguous*, it is highly unlikely it will lead to a *sufficient* explanation. Additionally it is also probably still intractable, and thus not *possible*.

Next, we will discuss the more global solution of adding a structure that captures aspects of form and meaning that iconic resemblance can be found in. Again we take a formalising by dialogue approach (Blokpoel & van Rooij, 2021; van Rooij & Blokpoel, 2020). In doing so, we start with questions that need answering to properly make our description *transparent* and *unambiguous*. Some of these could be: what type of structure is this? How is this structure added to the existing model? How is iconicity derived from this structure? Does this building in of iconicity *fix* the model by making the model *sufficient* and *possible*? If so, how?

One possible option is to use structure-mapping theory (Gentner, 1983; Gentner & Markman, 1997). Inspired by Taub (2000), this proposes that “the resemblance between the form and its meaning must be captured by a structured mapping between two representations” (Emmorey, 2014, p.1). Further research provides some empirical support for this point (Punselie et al., 2024). Using structure-mapping as a framework would allow us to incorporate iconicity into the model in a more holistic way. However, integration between structure-mapping theory and the non-ostensive model, as well as describing *how* iconicity would be captured by structured mappings, is a process that is not quick (Blokpoel et al., 2011). It could be made *transparent* and *unambiguous* through careful modelling, but it has not been done yet so is not quick.

This quick-fix suggestion is of such a scale that it cannot be known whether this will result in a *sufficient* model. It is different enough from the existing non-ostensive model that such a prediction is hard to make, even though it may seem promising on paper. A possible side-effect of this approach could be that adding structure mapping, even without incorporating iconicity, could lead to a *sufficient* model. This would have to be analysed specifically after any such fix is incorporated. For the *possibility* criterion, however, we have more information. It is known that structure-mapping as used for analogy is intractable (Blokpoel et al., 2019; van Rooij et al., 2008). It is this basis of structure mapping that we also suggest for incorporating iconicity. The intractability of structure mapping, combined with existing intractability, makes it very likely that the resulting model will also be intractable, which means that this quick-fix will not result in a model that is *possible*.

We started the analysis of this suggested quick-fix by stating there are (at least) two ways this can be interpreted. We proceeded to analyse both separately. The first option was to interpret the effect of iconicity as a within-model change and judge the efficacy from there. We

found that while this may be *quick*, there is no guarantee this *fix*-es the model. So while it is definitely possible to make a *transparent* and *unambiguous* description of this quick-fix, it is unlikely that the result will be *sufficient* to provide an explanation for communicative alignment. Finally, as this suggestion remains close to the non-ostensive model, its *impossibility* problems (i.e. intractability) are likely to remain a concern.

The second option is to look at iconicity as making use of inherent structure in the world to communicate more effectively. While it may *fix* some of our explanation if we manage to add iconicity as structure-mapping to the model, there is no guarantee that any such changes would be due to iconicity specifically, as there would be substantial changes to the model needed to add this structure. It is possible, though not quick, to create a *transparent* and *unambiguous* description of this model. However, all these changes are such that it would be an entirely new theory, and a mostly different explanation. This means that there is no guarantee of *sufficiency*. Further, there is a high chance of the resulting model being *impossible* due to intractability of structure mapping theory, as well possibly of the non-ostensive model. Thus, and including the necessary theoretical modelling make this not a *quick* fix.

2.3 Limit hypothesis space

Suggested quick-fix: In natural communication people don't consider all possible interpretations, so agents in the model should only consider a few relevant lexica, and not consider the full search space. Then it will work.

Another suggestion to quick-fix the non-ostensive model could be based on the idea that communicators only consider a small part of the in-principle hypothesis space (i.e., candidate meanings). This concrete notion of frugality is similar to other notions of frugality such as 'Good Enough' language comprehension and processing (Ferreira & Patson, 2007; Ferreira et al., 2002; Goldberg & Ferreira, 2022). People can come to an understanding that is good enough, even based on slightly inaccurate or non-optimal communication. Work by Keysar and Bly (1999) and Keysar et al. (2003) also shows other ways in which people do not necessarily use all possible information to come to understanding. Crucially, in the non-ostensive model this can only work if the small space considered contains the relevant hypotheses. This quick-fix is analogous to the central notion in Relevance Theory (Sperber & Wilson, 2001), namely that communication can be explained because people know which hypotheses are the relevant ones. We can interpret this to suggest a quick-fix where communicative alignment is conjectured to be possible when assuming a limited hypothesis space. Notably, the limited space should contain the relevant hypotheses. If it would not, then no good or even 'good enough' inferences can be made (Blokpoel et al., 2019; Kuipers, 2000; van Fraassen, 1985).

Bayesian models, like the (non-)ostensive model by van de Braak et al., 2021, often allow for considering all possible hypotheses (e.g., all possible lexica). That is, each in principle possible hypothesis (here lexicon) has a non-zero probability. However, it has been conjectured that people in the real world only consider a limited set of relevant hypotheses, rather than all possible ones (Keysar et al., 2003). Within this limited hypothesis space, which contains the *relevant* hypotheses, it is then more possible to reach communicative alignment. As both interlocutors are considering (the same) relevant hypotheses (i.e., lexica), this would explain why they can communicatively align by inferring the intended meaning.

We continue in our style of sketching the steps to turn this quick-fix statement into a computational suggestion. There are several questions that arise just from considering *how* the hypothesis space would be limited in a model. How would such a hypothesis space be limited? How is the number of hypotheses allowed determined? How is determined which hypotheses are within this limited space, i.e., which are the relevant ones?

It is not easy to quickly provide a computational answer to these questions that is also realistic. One might be tempted to approach this pragmatically by assigning agents a random subset of the hypothesis space. While this would be a quick choice, and can be described *transparently* and *unambiguously*, this will not result in a model that is *sufficient*; explaining communicative alignment entails explaining how people come to infer the relevant hypotheses. However, one might be fooled into believing it is sufficient, because if both agents are assigned the same random subset, the model might work (because it is hacked to work). Furthermore, it may result in a model that meets the *possibility* criterion, namely if the number of hypotheses is considerably limited (to only a handful of options) it could become computationally tractable. Ultimately, this approach to ‘limit hypothesis space’ is at best misleading and insufficient.

It is also possible to take a different approach to limiting the space by taking ‘relevance’ more seriously. The claim that ‘relevance helps’ might be grounded in Gricean maxims, which also underlie and inspire reasoning in Rational Speech Act (Frank & Goodman, 2012). Applicable here specifically would be the maxim of Relation, described in its briefest form as: “Be relevant” (Grice, 1975). This may seem a common sense suggestion that would resolve many problems before they could arise. This is easier said than done, however, as existing theories of relevance (such as Wilson and Sperber (2004)) are not computationally well defined, and may also bring more problems along (Blokpoel et al., 2012; Levinson, 1989; van Rooij et al., 2011; Woensdregt et al., 2024). Nonetheless, this still falls into the same fallacy we mentioned in the previous paragraph, where it may be quick to speak of, but ultimately neither the relevance maxim nor relevance theory computationally explain.

Readers who read this paper in order may wonder if the frame problem, mentioned earlier in Section 2.1, becomes relevant (pun intended) here again, and indeed it does. For a more detailed explanation of what the frame problem entails, see Box 1. Crucial for this quick-fix is that, to determine which part of the full hypothesis space is relevant, one cannot rule out having to use information from the full hypothesis space. This means that it is not possible to limit the hypothesis space to the relevant hypotheses to resolve the computational *possibility* and *sufficiency* issues.

The quick-fix suggests to ‘just’ limit the hypothesis space to make the model work. We discussed two possible approaches. The first was to randomly limit the hypothesis space that the model takes into account. While this might (no guarantee) result in a model that meets the criteria of *transparency*, *unambiguity*, and even *possibility*, it will definitely not be *sufficient* to explain the capacity. The second suggestion would take more involved modelling to create a *transparent* and *unambiguous* model to computationally explain relevance. Regardless of the nature of that explanation, e.g., whether or not relevance requires *all* relevant hypotheses or *some*, whether or not relevance is determined individually or in interaction, without further modelling we cannot yet know whether this will yield a *sufficient* model. However, similar to the “just add context” quick-fix, this second approach runs into *possibility* concerns involving the frame problem. This is not easy to resolve, because it is not possible to explain how people select the relevant hypotheses (and exclude irrelevant ones) in a model without using the full hypothesis space (see Box 1). Consequently, this suggestion will not yield a model that is both *possible* and *sufficient* for

explaining communicative alignment.

2.4 Create overlap in lexica

Suggested quick-fix: In natural communication people already use the same language, so you should just make the agents in the model have large/complete overlap in lexica. Then it will work.

In natural communication, people have overlap with their conversational partners in the language they use (i.e. they speak the same language, and/or know the meanings in the topic domain). However, the model allows for any degree of shared beliefs between two agents, including (almost) none. Researchers who might propose this quick-fix argue that people have a high or full overlap in initial shared meanings they can rely on to understand each other (Brennan & Clark, 1996; Clark, 1996; Schegloff, 1991).

In the model, agents share the same signals (words) and referents (meanings). In their inferences, agents consider all possible mappings between those words and meanings. Crucially, agents can have different prior probability distributions over all possible mappings. This means that agents may use the same word for a different (set of) meaning(s) or vice versa.

In this model, an overlap in lexica can be modelled as agents having identical prior probability distributions. However, this prior needs to be limited to a handful of (similar) lexica to get sufficient overlap in initial shared meanings for the quick-fix to work. This takes away the suitability of the (altered) non-ostensive model as an explanation of communicative alignment. A key component of communicative alignment is that it is possible to reach mutual understanding even if there previously is no shared understanding. Assuming shared understanding, i.e., assuming that which we aim to explain (cf. Woensdregt et al., 2024), means that the model is not a *sufficient* explanation for communicative alignment. This *fixed* model can only be a possible explanation for an entirely different cognitive capacity, namely one that assumes shared understanding.

This quick-fix may actually be more *quick* to implement than some of the ones discussed previously. The change in overlap of lexica is a smaller change that need not involve a complete redesign of the model, only a manipulation of the prior probability distribution of each agent. The overlap in lexica quick-fix might actually be *quick*, but does it satisfy our criteria for computational explanation laid out in Section 1.2?

With theoretical modelling this quick-fix could be *transparent* and *unambiguous*. However, this alteration is unlikely to be sufficient to ‘fix’ the model. If it even has a significant effect it is likely that slippage occurs from the capacity we wish to explain to other (perhaps related) capacities. As it would not fully explain communicative alignment, this cannot then be *sufficient* as a model. Additionally, it is unknown if the resulting model would end up tractable, given that the non-ostensive model suffers from intractability van de Braak et al. (2024).

There are a few conclusions for this quick-fix. Firstly, it is a tricky balance to make sure that any proposed changes don’t end up suggesting to transform the model for a different phenomenon and then applying the results to communicative alignment. This would only obfuscate explanation. Because of this it is not possible to state simply whether this model would result in a *sufficient* explanation. Next, similarly to some of the earlier quick-fixes, again this quick-fix may inherit

the intractability from the non-ostensive model. So finally, while there may be a way to approach this quick-fix in a *quick* way, that does not actually help *fix*.

2.5 Enrich the lexicon

Suggested quick-fix: Human communication is based on much richer and complicated forms. The representation of form in the model is too simple. Just add a richer notion of form to the lexica, then it will work.

Communication experts have, over the years, shown that human communication is extremely rich of form (Enfield, 2009). Humans use many different forms when communicating. Examples of this are multi-modality of communicative signals, co-speech gestures, facial expressions, body language, etc. (Levinson & Holler, 2014). The non-ostensive model only has one type of signal, and it is amodal, without connection to any of the forms or modes of human communication. Further, it is atomic, i.e., there is no information pertaining to the relationship between signal and meaning, other than the relationship being there or not. Such atomic representations are not able to capture multi-modality of language where different forms of language interact with each other to convey a meaning through structured content (cf. Özyürek, 2014; Punselie et al., 2024). Additionally, it is discrete; signals are categorical tokens, not continuous ones (cf. Pouw & Fuchs, 2022, which uses continuous multimodal signals). We interpret the quick-fix to suggest enriching the existing lexica within the model to better capture the richness of communication. This interpretation quite clearly renders the quick-fix not quick, but it is worth-while to explore how it can be *transparent*, *unambiguous*, *sufficient* and *possible*.

As before, we can ask several theoretical questions that need to be answered. Firstly, what sort of forms need to be added into a lexicon? Do these need to necessarily be compound (as implied by co-speech gestures and multi-modality)? Are there other aspects of form that need to be included? Do we need to distinguish between spoken word, written word, and gesture? Do we need to use continuous signals as opposed to the current discrete ones?

It is far from trivial what should be incorporated in the lexicon in the model to support all forms of communication. Hence, this quick-fix cannot be quick. Further, even if the incorporations are determined, the next important question becomes how to computationally represent these elements in a model. For example, what constitutes a signal in this updated model?

Answering these questions is not *quick* because all of them take careful consideration to describe in a *transparent* and *unambiguous* way.

For the sake of the argument, let us state that it is possible to successfully incorporate different forms into our lexicon. That means that each lexicon still has signals and referents and mappings between the two. However, each signal in a lexicon now has more richness, though the shape of the lexicon is unchanged. Now, do we think these hypothetical changes can *fix* the model? Perhaps. It is hard to give a definite answer about something that is undesigned and undeveloped. Hence, it is unknown if the revised model is *sufficient* to computationally explain communicative alignment.

A further consideration is that this model may once again be intractable and thus *impossible*. This is because these changes stay within the framework of the non-ostensive model, which is intractable. Adding a complex component to the model is unlikely to resolve this intractability.

However, this would need to be mathematically proven for the revised model, as intuitions about what makes a model tractable are often incorrect (Blokpoel et al., 2011; van Rooij, 2008; van Rooij et al., 2008).

As we describe in Section 1.2, our aim, that which we model for, is to explain the capacity for communicative alignment. If this richness of lexicon helps achieve a positive outcome for the model, that does not necessarily mean it is directly a good explanation. If this richness of lexicon is well-developed, and all elements can be traced back to their origins, this may well be a good explanation. However, if it is unclear or unspecified how these different forms come together to enrich the lexicon, we still are left with an incomplete explanation.

To conclude, this quick-fix suggestion most certainly is not *quick*, as it will take significant development to transform this suggestion into a model adjustment. As seen earlier, it is thus not possible at this stage to state with certainty whether this model adjustment would then be *sufficient* to fix the model. Further, as the suggested quick-fix will only add dimensions to the existing non-ostensive model, it is highly likely that the quick-fix will inherit the intractability present in the non-ostensive model, and thus not be *possible*.

3 Intermediate conclusions

We analysed five different quick-fix solutions for their efficacy in providing a model that can explain the capacity for communicative alignment. For each quick-fix, we evaluated whether it is *quick*, and if it fixes computational explanation along the four criteria: *transparent*, *unambiguous*, *sufficient*, and *possible* (see Section 1.2). In this section, we build on the analysis to highlight common patterns in the theoretical problems of the quick-fixes, and reflect on the consequences for computationally explaining communicative alignment.

Quick-fix	Abbreviation
Context	C
Iconicity within model	IW
Iconicity generic	IG
Limit hypothesis space within model	LW
Limit hypothesis space generic	LG
Overlap of lexica	O
Enrich the lexicon	E

Table 3: Abbreviations we use in this section to refer to the quick-fixes in text.

3.1 Interpretation of the results

Whereas previously, we analysed each quick-fix for its theoretical problems, here we turn this analysis upside down. We start from the side of the theoretical problems to reveal two things: (1) quick-fixes share common problems and (2) some theoretical problems are interrelated (but not reducible). Table 3 and 4 provide an overview of the quick-fix analysis from Section 2.

Quick-fixes that are not quick (C, IG, LG, E) are currently not *transparent* and not *unambiguous* (Figure 4). In general, developing computational explanations that are *transparent* and *unambiguous* takes time that cannot be taken for granted (see also Rich et al., 2021).

Figure 4: A quick-fix that is not *unambiguous* and not *transparent* will not be quick.

The *transparency* and *unambiguity* criteria mostly revolve around the quality of the *formal description*. Quick-fixes that lead to a *transparent* and *unambiguous* formal description (IW and LW) can be quick (Figure 5). We observe that these types of quick-fixes stay very close to the original model. Hence, they are unlikely to be *sufficient* and *possible*.

Figure 5: A quick-fix that is *unambiguous* and *transparent* can be quick. A quick-fix close to the original model is likely to be *unambiguous* and *transparent*.

The results on *sufficiency* and *possibility* are more complex, as they relate to the quality of the *explanation* the quick-fix provides. Only *transparent* and *unambiguous* formal models can in principle be analysed for *sufficiency* and *possibility*. Hence, we have a dichotomy: Cases where a *transparent* and *unambiguous* model is available (IW and LW) and cases where this is not (C, IG, LG, O, and E). While each case requires its individual analysis, we observe that in general *transparent* and *unambiguous* models are not (likely to be) *sufficient* (Figure 6).

Figure 6: A quick-fix that is *unambiguous* and *transparent* is likely to not result in a model that is *sufficient*.

We further observe that for cases without *transparent* and *unambiguous* models, it is not possible to know in advance whether or not it is *sufficient* or *possible* (Figure 7). Indeed, this highlights

that often it is not possible to know in advance whether a suggested fix will resolve all theoretical problems and result in a model that can provide a good computational explanation of communicative alignment.

Figure 7: For quick-fix that is not transparent and not unambiguous it is unknown whether it will be possible and/or sufficient.

Table 4: A table giving an overview of the quick-fixes set against the different criteria, showing which quick-fix matches which criterion.

		quick	transparent	unambiguous	sufficient	possible
C	context	no	could be	could be	unknown	no: frame problem
IW	iconicity: within model	yes	yes	yes	highly unlikely	possibly no
IG	iconicity: generic	no	could be	could be	unknown	unknown
LW	limit: within model	yes	yes	yes	no	possibly yes
LG	limit: generic	no	could be	could be	unknown	no: frame problem
O	overlap	possibly	could be	yes	no	possibly yes
E	enrich	no	could be	could be	unknown	no: intractable

However, we can reason about what we think likely to happen in all these situations.

An example of this is the *sufficiency* of IW, which we state is highly unlikely to be *sufficient*. At this stage we cannot know for certain, but given the changes suggested and the base of the non-ostensive model, we make an informed estimation that while it still might be able to result in a *sufficient* model to explain communicative alignment, it is highly unlikely.

In the cases in which the *sufficiency* is unknown (C, IG, LG, E), that is usually the case because the suggested quick-fix would result in a substantially different model. Because of that, it is harder to estimate its *sufficiency* as it is not possible to know ahead of computational modelling what changes will result in a sufficient model.

Regarding the *possibility* criterion, there we find the most varied answers, yet we can see some

general commonalities which we discuss here.

If the *possibility* is listed as ‘possibly no’, there are two reasons mentioned. The first is the frame problem, which arises in **C** and **LG**. The frame problem is believed to be unsolvable (see Box 1), so unless a solution for that problem is found, these quick-fixes will not be possible.

The second reason is intractability. The Tractable Cognition thesis states that any model of cognition must be tractable to be considered a plausible explanation (van Rooij, 2008). Any model that is intractable does not meet the criterion of *possibility*. This is a problem in the non-ostensive model, and due to how the intractability is present in many components in that model, it is likely to be inherited by the quick-fix models that stay close to the non-ostensive model. Hence, intractability is a guaranteed theoretical problem for **E**, and a probable theoretical problem for **IW**. Intractability, similarly to the frame problem, is also not a fixable problem, and will remain an unfixable problem, unless the conjecture $P=NP$ happens to be proven (something deemed so unlikely and difficult in mathematics that there is a million dollar reward set out for the person who can prove this conjecture to be true). Readers familiar with intractability work may wonder why we do not suggest fixed-parameter tractability at this stage. While it is possible to do a parametrised complexity analysis to search for a fixed-parameter tractable model (Kwisthout, 2018; van Rooij, 2008; van Rooij & Wareham, 2007; van de Pol et al., 2018), this is not a quick process, and also not one with guaranteed (fixed-parameter) tractability. There is also no guarantee that the resulting model retains any sufficiency of explanation that it may have in its intractable state.

That leaves the ‘possibly yes’ and ‘unknown’ answers for the *possibility* criterion. While we still cannot guarantee in advance whether a model is possible, we still use ‘possibly yes’ so what does that mean? These are the ‘limit hypothesis space, within model’ (**LW**) and ‘create overlap in lexica’ (**O**) suggestions. These quick-fixes suggest constraining the hypothesis space. If the space is constrained strongly enough, as function of the input, it may yet be possible that this model is not intractable. However, the ‘possibly’ in this case should not be disregarded. While there is a possibility that the model is not intractable in the end, and thus *could* be *possible*, there is still no guarantee of this as we have done no formal proof, and the likelihood of this is not high. So any ‘possibly yes’ in the table should not be received with the relief of problems solved, but rather with the scepticism of something that may work but also may not, all under very specific conditions.

The single ‘unknown’ *possibility* entry in Table 4 is the quick-fix that suggests to integrate iconicity in a generic way (**IG**). The resulting model of this quick-fix will be necessarily different from the non-ostensive model, and as such it is unknown whether this model will encounter possibility problems.

After discussing the results presented in the table in some detail, let us consider some more overarching conclusions.

We can see that the entries for *transparent* and *unambiguous* are identical for most quick-fixes. This stems from both of these being main goals of the model formalisation process. The process of making a theory *transparent* involves making explicit the ideas of how the theory works. It is then possible to evaluate whether this written-down version indeed captures a theory, as we illustrated with the number guessing game in the introduction. During this evaluation and refining process, ambiguity is one of the things that can be focused on. Hence, if the steps to formally model a quick-fix are taken, then it *could* be made *transparent*. In that process of coming

to a *transparent* description, it *could be* that the description is also *unambiguous*.

Next, we stated in Section 1.4 a few of the problems with the non-ostensive model. If a quick-fix results in a model that is still very similar to the non-ostensive model, the quick-fix may also inherit these same problems. This especially shows in the quick-fixes with tractability concerns, or the quick-fixes deemed a priori to be *impossible*.

3.2 Consequences for modelling Communicative Alignment

Communicative alignment is the capacity people have to come to shared understanding in cases where such shared understanding does not initially exist. The non-ostensive model was developed to explain this capacity, but it has a few rather large problems. Firstly, it does not actually capture the phenomenon as we see it occur in the world. Rather, while the agents in the model (van de Braak et al., 2021) perceive that they have high understanding, their mutual factual understanding is poor (at chance level). The model cannot provide a *sufficient* explanation. Additionally, the non-ostensive model is intractable, meaning that it is not a plausible model to explain the capacity, it does not meet the *possibility* criterion.

The five (or seven, if we count the variations) quick-fixes introduced in this paper are quick-fix solutions aimed at resolving or avoiding the problems present in the non-ostensive model and creating a new model that can explain communicative alignment adequately. We reflect here on how these quick-fixes do not succeed at the goal of quickly fixing the problems with the non-ostensive model.

Of the quick-fixes discussed in this paper, a few could possibly be *quick*, but none are guaranteed to be a fix for the existing problems, and some will only exacerbate the existing problems. We group some results together by characteristics that we find through our analyses. These groupings could be considered different categories of quick-fixes, which we will return to in Section 4.4.

Quick-fixes that stay close to the existing model may be quick, though not always. They can be quick because there may be less formal modelling to do to come to a *transparent* and *unambiguous* description of the quick-fix model. However, as these suggestions remain so close to the original non-ostensive model, they cannot ‘fix’ the model, and often inherit the problems present in the non-ostensive models. We see this in the within-model variation of the iconicity quick-fix, as well as the overlapping lexica model.

Next, we see some quick-fixes that are grounded in substantial communication literature (Clark, 1996; Clark & Brennan, 1991; Dingemanse, Blasi, et al., 2015; Levinson, 2006; Perniss et al., 2010; Punselie et al., 2024; Taub, 2000), but are of such a scale that they cannot be quick to incorporate. Examples of this are the adding context and adding iconicity quick-fixes. These fixes are so substantive it will take reworking of large parts of the non-ostensive model as well as formal modelling specifically to the quick-fix, these are definitely not quick. Furthermore, bear in mind that even if the quick-fix is formalised, there is still no guarantee that these will result in a fixed model.

Then there are those quick-fixes which can lead to obscuring explanation. In most cases this happens when in the process of a fix, the focus is not on the capacity communicative alignment. If a fix leads to a model that can potentially ‘work’, the most important criterion to determine whether it actually ‘works’ is to ensure that the explanation it provides is one for

communicative alignment. That is, is the explanation provided sufficient to capture all known aspects of communicative alignment. An example of this is one of the points discussed in ‘create an overlap in lexica’. In this case, if both agents have such an overlap in lexica that there is no asymmetry between the two agents (read: all their signal-referent mappings are identical), this does not match communicative alignment. In communicative alignment specifically the point is about reaching mutual understanding in the absence of such mutual understanding initially. Quick-fixing a model so that the agents cannot misunderstand each other does not match this capacity, as then the agents have shared understanding at the *beginning* of their interaction.

Additionally, we also have the quick-fixes where the quick-fixes are more based in computational cognitive modelling choices that relate to the type of model the non-ostensive model is, rather than grounding in communication literature, such as the limiting hypothesis space quick-fix. These fixes are aimed to fix the problems in the non-ostensive model based on the type of model it is (i.e. a Bayesian model with a large hypothesis space), rather than on the capacity. In this quick-fix it is thus also possible to lose track of the capacity, because the fix is suggested to superficially fix the problems in the existing non-ostensive model. Even when a fix does not obscure the capacity, there is still no guarantee it will be a successful quick-fix, and indeed in this example there is also the possibility that in trying to fix one problem (intractability) we get another in return (the frame problem). And that with no guarantees that the model resulting from the quick-fix is actually fixed of its intractability problem.

We see quick-fixes unable to solve the existing problems with the non-ostensive model of communicative alignment, such as the intractability problem, or the cognitive scope violation problem. In addition to this, some quick-fixes succeed in adding new and exciting problems to the model. We see this most clearly in the add context and limit hypothesis space quick-fixes, which both add the frame problem as a concern. There are many different theoretical problems in cognitive science. Thus it is not inconceivable that any suggested addition may end up adding more theoretical problems to a quick-fixed model.

Even in the cases where a quick-fix does not seemingly add extra problems at this stage, it is never possible to a priori state whether a fix will be sufficient and possible. A suggestion can be the start to developing a new model, to follow up on the non-ostensive model, and can, in turn, be analysed for its sufficiency and possibility. However, this is not quick, and with any such work there is no guarantee that a suggested change will result in a ‘fixed’ model.

In conclusion, it is not easy to explain communicative alignment. Previous work shows that a well-thought out, *transparent* and *unambiguous* model can still be *impossible* (due to intractability) and *insufficient* (the model behaviour not showing communicative alignment). This paper shows that these fundamental problems cannot be quickly fixed. A quick-fix suggestion will not resolve existing problems, and may even add more problems, or obscure explanation. In the introduction we introduced this capacity clearly enough to show that this is a capacity that people do have. Yet, despite our best efforts, it remains a capacity that is not easy to computationally explain. Any cognitive scientist subscribed to computationalism will not be able to use quick-fix solutions to solve existing theoretical problems with their explanations.

4 Metatheoretical map-typology

We have a further contribution to make. The quick-fix analysis applies specifically to models of communicative alignment. In this Section, we argue that the types discovered through this analysis can be abstracted more broadly to other computational models and modelling of cognitive capacities. We take the different groupings described in the previous section, and use those to develop a metatheoretical typology of quick-fixes and the pitfalls they are susceptible to.

Next to the descriptions of the categories as we see them appear in the specific quick-fixes, we use analogies to convey these categories of quick-fixes. We use analogy for two purposes. Firstly, as a means to clearly abstract these categories (cf. Gentner & Asmuth, 2019; Gick & Holyoak, 1983; Skorstad et al., 1988) from the domain of communicative alignment, making it possible for other quick-fixes in other domains to be critically analysed. Secondly, the analogies serve to translate a high-level meta-scientific analysis to a broader computational science audience (cf. Coll et al., 2005; Newton & Newton, 1995).

All analogies we create and use in this section are map-themed. This analogy is inspired by discussions of map-territory⁸ confusion in Guest and Martin (2024). A map-territory confusion, applied to the case of communicative alignment, would conflate the capabilities of the non-ostensive model with the human capacity of communicative alignment. The confusion is to mistake the model for *being* the actual capacity. While explicit confusions may be few and far between, more often they are implicit. For example, one may reason (incorrectly) that because the non-ostensive model (the map) cannot communicate successfully in the absence of ostensive signalling, neither can humans (the territory) communicate successfully in the absence of ostensive signalling.

In this paper we use maps and their territory *not* in the sense of the map-territory confusion described above. Rather, we create an analogy, using maps, to convey the typology of quick-fixes that we determine from our analyses. While we use maps and territories as analogous for models and cognitive capacities respectively, we do not claim that any model *is* a (specific type of) map. Nor do we claim that a cognitive capacity is exactly a territory that can be mapped. Each map will be viewed through the lens of someone using that map for a specific purpose, analogous to using a model to explain a specific capacity. Each map type named will initially have a problem when being used for its purpose, analogous to a model having problems and not being able to explain the capacity. Next, a quick-fix will be applied; a change of the map intended to fix the problem. The accompanying illustrations show how this quick-fix would result in a changed map. We use the analogy to show how this type of quick-fix does not end up completely solving the problem with each map, in each of the different ways stated in the previous section.

We reintroduce each type here, with a name and a short description.

Oversimplification. Simplifying the explanation to such extent that it cannot explain the capacity.

Excessiveness. Adding many more details to the model without the guarantee that they will contribute to an explanation for the capacity. They also cannot be quick.

⁸See also Korzybski (1958, p. xvii): “the map is *not* the territory,” which expresses the idea that “everything and anything that humans formulate” (i.e. maps) are not the thing they represent (i.e. territory).

Obfuscation. Tacitly changing the capacity-to-be-explained which means the ‘fixed’ model cannot explain the original capacity.

Mis-focussing. Hyperfocussing on details of the model, rather than the capacity, to such an extent that it still cannot explain the capacity.

Exacerbation. Adding additional theoretical problems, while not (guarantee to) solve any existing theoretical problem.

We discuss these quick-fix types in order. This list of types is not exhaustive. There may be types found in different analyses or domains that we did not have in the analysis in this paper. Further, the types are not mutually exclusive: a specific quick-fix from Section 2 may exhibit more than one of the above types.

4.1 Oversimplification

A quick-fix of this type is perhaps quick, but already confirmed to be insufficient because it is too simplistic. In this case, the quick-fix suggestion is possibly quick to execute. However, it is often a suggestion that simplifies so much of the model that the model will not capture the complexity of the capacity.

For an analogy, let us take a situation in which we want to find a way from point A to point B. We have a map of the area, with points A and B indicated, and also a mountain range in between. There are no available roads indicated on the map to pass from A to B, with the mountains in the way.

This quick-fix is to just draw a line from point A to point B on the map (Figure 8).

While a line on a map may indicate a road, this will not magically manifest a road in reality. Maybe there is a path through the mountains to get to B, and maybe there is not. Regardless, drawing a line on a map will not relate to where any such road may be in the real world.

This represents an oversimplification in an attempt to fix the map. While it is definitely a quick solution to just draw a line on a map – quicker than finding the road in reality and painstakingly keeping track of where it runs exactly to draw an accurate map – it does not actually help with having a map that shows how to get from A to B.

4.2 Excessiveness

Excessiveness may seem in some ways opposite to oversimplification. This type suggests to add an overabundance of extra information to solve the problems. The difficulty with this, as we discuss in the previous section, is that this cannot be quick, as there are many deliberations needed to properly integrate all the extra information into the existing model. Additionally, all this extra information provides no guarantee for being able to explain the capacity.

Take again a map with points A and B, separated by a mountain range (see Figure 9). The (not-so-quick) fix to this map is to add a lot of extra detail to the map to more accurately reflect the terrain. We thus add snow on the mountains, gravel and rocks on the ground, draw in all

Figure 8: Two pencil drawings of a map in two versions. On the left two points, A and B, separated by a mountain range. On the right two points, A and B, still separated by a mountain range, but this time with a line running straight from A to B.

the trees, indicate areas where goats and cows roam, draw where water flows, and anything else we can think of. All these additions make the map horrendously dense. Even if any possible roads are included in this broad addition process, it is so much extra information that the map becomes hard to read. While it is possible that this map gives enough information in principle to plan a route from A to B, this is not a given. Even when it does contain enough information, it may not be able to serve its purpose, namely finding a route from A to B.

Figure 9: Two pen and pencil sketches of two points, A and B, with a mountain range between them. The mountain range in the left is in pencil and unannotated. The mountain range on the right is deeply detailed and has not just mountains drawn on, but trees added, rivers and a lake added, snow added, goats added, roads added, and rocks added. The image on the right has a legend matching all colours of the added marks to their meaning.

4.3 Obfuscation

Obfuscation is the type that inspired the title for this paper: the quick-fixes that obscure explanation. Quick-fixes in this category tend to solve the problem for a different capacity, rather than the target one. Regardless of the validity of this explanation for the other capacity, it will

obscure explanation for the target capacity. This because the explanation may be claimed as concerning the target capacity. Then, we can be presented with an explanation for the target capacity which cannot actually explain the target capacity.

Consider a metro map. The goal is still to get from point A to point B, but by using the metro, rather than walking. However, the map, as can be seen in Figure 10 has a large ink stain, making part of the map illegible. A possible solution to still get from A to B is to just get out of the metro at the last station visible on the A side of the stain, let's call this station C. From station C, we then walk to the station closest to the stain on the other side (station D), and use the metro to get from D to B. For this we add the walking time (or route) to the map.

While it is now possible to use this map to get from point A to point B, the purpose of this map was to be able to use the metro for the whole journey. Getting out and walking part of the distance may solve the problem of "getting to station B", but it does not solve the problem of "getting from station A to station B by metro", though it may seem to.

Figure 10: A pen drawing of two points, A and B, marked on a metro map. The metro map has an ink stain in the middle, obscuring some of the stations. The image on the right shows a dotted line with a figure next to it indicating a walking path between two stations where the metro line cannot be seen.

4.4 Mis-focussing

Mis-focussing is inspired by quick-fixes that are so fixated on details of the model, that they do not take the cognitive capacity into account. The quick-fix will thus not further the explanation of the capacity.

We once again wish to travel by metro from point A to point B. However, in this example, we do not have a metro map, but rather a satellite map (see Figure 11). It does have metro stations marked, but it does not include which metro stations are connected to which.

The quick-fix in this case is to simplify the map from a satellite map to a roadmap. With marked roads, and less distractors from the satellite detail, the map may be easier to read for navigation. However, it still does not include the metro lines, because it is a road map, and not a metro map. So even though a change was made to the map, it is not one that has any bearing on solving the problems that lie between the map and its purpose. With the information on the map, it is still

not possible to plan a route (by metro) from metro station A to metro station B.

Figure 11: A satellite map on the left, and a road map of the same area on the right. Both maps are marked with several red dots that indicate metro stations in this area. Points A and B are marked on the map, each next to a red dot.

4.5 Exacerbation

Exacerbation is the type of pitfall in which the quick-fix only adds problems, rather than solving any problems, exacerbating the current state of affairs. In addition to adding new problems, quick-fixes of this type generally do not solve any initial theoretical problems.

For this map analogy we go back to the mountain range maps, see Figure 12. We once again want to get from point A to point B, but there is a mountain range in the way and no paths or roads marked. An exacerbation quick-fix to this problem is to just cut the mountain range out of the map. The reasoning behind this would be: if there is no mountain range on the map then we can easily walk from point A to point B. However, this does not mean that the mountain range has also vanished from reality. Now there are added problems. We still have the initial problems of needing to cross the mountain range without a suitable path on the map to guide us. Additionally to the mountains being in the way between points A and B, our map now has a hole, which removes even the limited information we had. We have only increased the theoretical problems we need to deal with.

4.6 Synthesis of the typology

In this paper we have developed a typology, using maps as an analogy, to capture the types of pitfalls quick-fixes are susceptible to. We propose this typology is a meta-theoretical contribution to the wider field of cognitive science, beyond the specific explanandum of communicative alignment. This typology can be used both retroactively and proactively.

Retroactively it can be used in e.g. the following scenario. Say we take a model with (theoretical) problems, that has had a quick-fix applied to it. Critical analysis of the resulting quick-fixed model ensures it can be compared to the different map-problem types. When a comparison has been found, the typology can help understand why the quick-fix did not result in a successful model.

Figure 12: Two figures showing a pencil drawn map with points *A* and *B* and a mountain range. On the left, the mountain range is in between points *A* and *B*. On the right, the part containing the mountain range has been cut out, showing the author's desk through the hole cut in the map.

The map-typology can also be used proactively. Take a situation such as we started this paper with. We have a cognitive capacity and a model to attempt to explain that capacity. Given a suggestion to fix the model, we can compare that suggestion to the typology, and use that comparison to judge whether the suggestion falls in one of the pitfalls of quick-fixes.

The types we defined in this paper are not mutually exclusive nor exhaustive. The quick-fixes we analysed in this paper often fall under more than one type. In any analysis that use the map typology, it is therefore important to investigate a suggested quick-fix in detail to discover all types of pitfall they may fall under.

5 Conclusions

This paper was written to answer the question whether quick-fix solutions can help increase understanding by solving known problems with understanding misunderstanding. We proposed a metatheoretical framework for assessing these quick-fixes, based on four criteria of *transparency*, *unambiguity*, *sufficiency*, and *possibility*. We applied this analysis framework to quick-fixes aimed at quickly fixing the non-ostensive model for communicative alignment. We showed that none of these quick-fixes would *quickly* result in a model that would *fix* the existing theoretical problems of the non-ostensive model.

Quick-fix solutions may be quick to suggest, but they often require more thinking through if they are even aimed at solving the actual problems with a model. This is evident during the quick-fix analyses we performed, where we needed to take several reasoning steps before being able to even analyse the suggestion. Next, quick-fixes require careful and explicit formalisation before they can truly be analysed and determined whether they will solve the problem. In the absence of such a formalism it is not possible to critically analyse a quick-fixed model. Without this critical analysis, quick-fixes cannot be assumed to make a big difference to the explanatory power of a model. For some quick-fixes it is possible to know in advance that they *will not* result in a sufficient and possible explanation. An example of this is if we can already determine the

model to be an insufficient explanation. However, it is *never* possible to know a priori whether a quick-fix will be sufficient and possible. In all cases, it is not easy to quick-fix around existing theoretical problems. If a current model has theoretical problems (as the non-ostensive model does), these cannot be guaranteed to be solved with a quick-fix.

This analysis inspired the creation of a metatheoretical map-typology, illustrating common pitfalls in trying to *fix* models. This typology can be applied to any computational explanation of any cognitive capacity, not just communicative alignment. We hope that this work inspires other metatheoreticians to adopt this methodology and our typology to other domains of cognitive science. Doing so will contribute to more sound theoretical foundations of our fields.

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Images of the fruits in Figure 1 designed by macrovector/Freepik. Satellite- and Roadmaps of Amsterdam in Figure 10 sourced from Satellietdataportal.nl.

Author contributions

The below list of author contributions was created in accordance with the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) (<https://credit.niso.org/>), which is made available under (Creative Commons 4.0 (CC-BY)).

LvdB: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft

IvR: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft

MD: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

IT: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

MB: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft

References

- Adolfi, F., van de Braak, L., & Woensdregt, M. (2024). From empirical problem-solving to theoretical problem-finding perspectives on the cognitive sciences. *Computational Brain & Behavior*, 7(4), 572–587. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-024-00216-6>
- Albert, S., & de Ruiter, J. P. (2018). Repair: The interface between interaction and cognition. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, 10(2), 279–313. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12339>

- Barry, T., Griffith, J., de Rossi, S., & Hermans, D. (2014). Meet the fribbles: Novel stimuli for use within behavioural research. *Frontiers in Psychology, 5*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00103>
- Blokpoel, M. (2018). Sculpting computational-level models. *Topics in Cognitive Science, 10*(3), 641–648. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12282>
- Blokpoel, M., van Kesteren, M., Stolk, A., Haselager, P., Toni, I., & van Rooij, I. (2012). Recipient design in human communication: Simple heuristics or perspective taking? *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 6*, 253. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2012.00253>
- Blokpoel, M., & van Rooij, I. (2021). *Theoretical modeling for cognitive science and psychology*. <https://computationalcognitivescience.github.io/lovelace/home>
- Blokpoel, M., Wareham, T., Haselager, P., Toni, I., & van Rooij, I. (2011). The computational costs of recipient design and intention recognition in communication. *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*.
- Blokpoel, M., Wareham, T., Haselager, P., Toni, I., & van Rooij, I. (2019). Deep analogical inference as the origin of hypotheses. *The Journal of Problem Solving, 11*(1). <https://doi.org/10.7771/1932-6246.1197>
- Bonanno, G. (2015). Reasoning about strategies and rational play in dynamic games. In J. van Benthem, S. Ghosh, & R. Verbrugge (Eds.), *Models of strategic reasoning: Logics, games, and communities* (pp. 34–62). Springer. Retrieved March 25, 2025, from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-48540-8_2
- Brennan, S. E., & Clark, H. H. (1996). Conceptual pacts and lexical choice in conversation. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition, 22*(6), 127–149.
- Clark, A. (2006). Material symbols. *Philosophical Psychology, 19*(3), 291–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09515080600689872>
- Clark, H. H. (1996). *Using language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Clark, H. H. (1997). Dogmas of understanding. *Discourse Processes, 23*(3), 567–598. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01638539709545003>
- Clark, H. H., & Brennan, S. E. (1991). Grounding in communication. In L. B. Resnick, J. M. Levine, & S. D. Teasley (Eds.), *Perspectives on socially shared cognition* (pp. 127–149, Vol. 13). APA Books.
- Clark, H. H., & Schaefer, E. (1987). Collaborating on contributions to conversations. *Language and Cognitive Processes, 2*(1), 19–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01690968708406350>
- Clark, H. H., & Wilkes-Gibbs, D. (1986). Referring as a collaborative process. *Cognition, 22*(1), 1–39. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(86\)90010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(86)90010-7)
- Clift, R. (2016, September 8). *Conversation analysis*. Cambridge University Press.
- Coll, R. K., France, B., & Taylor, I. (2005). The role of models/and analogies in science education: Implications from research. *International Journal of Science Education, 27*(2), 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950069042000276712>
- Cooper, R., DeJong, D. V., Forsythe, R., & Ross, T. W. (1992). Communication in coordination games. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics, 107*(2), 739–771. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118488>
- Cooper, R. (1999). *Coordination games*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511609428>
- Cummins, R. C. (2000). “how does it work” versus “what are the laws?”: Two conceptions of psychological explanation. In F. Keil & R. A. Wilson (Eds.), *Explanation and cognition, 117-145*. MIT Press.
- de Jaegher, H., Di Paolo, E., & Gallagher, S. (2010). Can social interaction constitute social cognition? *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 14*(10), 441–447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2010.06.009>

- de Ruiter, J. P., Noordzij, M. L., Newman-Norlund, S., Hagoort, P., & Toni, I. (2007). On the origin of intentions. In *Sensorimotor foundations of higher cognition* (pp. 601–618). Oxford University Press.
- de Weerd, H., Verbrugge, R., & Verheij, B. (2015). Higher-order theory of mind in the tacit communication game. *Biologically Inspired Cognitive Architectures*, *11*, 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bica.2014.11.010>
- Degen, J., Trotske, A., Scontras, G., Wittenberg, E., & Goodman, N. D. (2019). Definitely, maybe: A new experimental paradigm for investigating the pragmatics of evidential devices across languages. *Journal of Pragmatics*, *140*, 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2018.11.015>
- Dingemanse, M., Blasi, D. E., Lupyan, G., Christiansen, M. H., & Monaghan, P. (2015). Arbitrariness, iconicity, and systematicity in language. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *19*(10), 603–615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.07.013>
- Dingemanse, M., & Enfield, N. J. (2024). Interactive repair and the foundations of language. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *28*(1), 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.09.003>
- Dingemanse, M., Liesenfeld, A., Rasenber, M., Albert, S., Ameka, F. K., Birhane, A., Bolis, D., Cassell, J., Clift, R., Cuffari, E., de Jaegher, H., Novaes, C. D., Enfield, N. J., Fusaroli, R., Gregoromichelaki, E., Hutchins, E., Konvalinka, I., Milton, D., Rączaszek-Leonardi, J., ... Wiltschko, M. (2023). Beyond single-mindedness: A figure-ground reversal for the cognitive sciences. *Cognitive Science*, *47*(1), e13230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.13230>
- Dingemanse, M., Roberts, S. G., Baranova, J., Blythe, J., Drew, P., Floyd, S., Gisladottir, R. S., Kendrick, K. H., Levinson, S. C., Manrique, E., Rossi, G., & Enfield, N. J. (2015). Universal principles in the repair of communication problems (S. Kotz, Ed.). *PLoS ONE*, *10*(9), e0136100. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136100>
- Dynel, M. (2020). To say the least: Where deceptively withholding information ends and lying begins. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, *12*(2), 555–582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12379>
- Egan, F. (2017). Function-theoretic explanation. In *Explanation and integration in mind and brain science*. Oxford University Press.
- Eijk, L., Rasenber, M., Arnese, F., Blokpoel, M., Dingemanse, M., Doeller, C. F., Ernestus, M., Holler, J., Milivojevic, B., Özyürek, A., Pouw, W., van Rooij, I., Schriefers, H., Toni, I., Trujillo, J., & Bögels, S. (2022). The CABB dataset: A multimodal corpus of communicative interactions for behavioural and neural analyses. *NeuroImage*, *264*, 119734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2022.119734>
- Elffers, J., & Hollingdale, R. J. (1976). *Tangram: The ancient chinese shapes game*. McGraw-Hill.
- Emmorey, K. (2014). Iconicity as structure mapping. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *369*(1651), 20130301. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0301>
- Enfield, N. J. (2009). *The anatomy of meaning: Speech, gesture, and composite utterances*. Cambridge University Press.
- Enfield, N. J. (2013, November 26). *Relationship thinking: Agency, enchrony, and human sociality*. Oxford University Press.
- Ferreira, F., Bailey, K. G., & Ferraro, V. (2002). Good-enough representations in language comprehension. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, *11*(1), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.00158>
- Ferreira, F., & Patson, N. D. (2007). The ‘good enough’ approach to language comprehension. *Language and Linguistics Compass*, *1*(1), 71–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-818X.2007.00007.x>
- Fodor, J. A. (1983). *The modularity of the mind: An essay on faculty psychology*. MIT Press.

- Fodor, J. A. (2001). *The mind doesn't work that way: The scope and limits of computational psychology*. MIT Press.
- Frank, M. C., & Goodman, N. D. (2012). Predicting pragmatic reasoning in language games. *Science*, *336*(6084), 998–998. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1218633>
- Fusaroli, R., Rączaszek-Leonardi, J., & Tylén, K. (2014). Dialog as interpersonal synergy. *New Ideas in Psychology*, *32*, 147–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newideapsych.2013.03.005>
- Galantucci, B., & Garrod, S. (2011). Experimental semiotics: A review. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, *5*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2011.00011>
- Galati, A., & Brennan, S. E. (2021). What is retained about common ground? distinct effects of linguistic and visual co-presence. *Cognition*, *215*, 104809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2021.104809>
- Gentner, D. (1983). Structure-mapping: A theoretical framework for analogy*. *Cognitive Science*, *7*(2), 155–170. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15516709cog0702_3
- Gentner, D. (2019). Cognitive science is and should be pluralistic. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, *11*(4), 884–891. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12459>
- Gentner, D., & Asmuth, J. (2019). Metaphoric extension, relational categories, and abstraction. *Language, Cognition and Neuroscience*, *34*(10), 1298–1307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23273798.2017.1410560>
- Gentner, D., & Markman, A. B. (1997). Structure mapping in analogy and similarity. *American Psychologist*, *12*.
- Gick, M. L., & Holyoak, K. J. (1983). Schema induction and analogical transfer. *Cognitive Psychology*, *15*(1), 1–38. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(83\)90002-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(83)90002-6)
- Goldberg, A. E., & Ferreira, F. (2022). Good-enough language production. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *26*(4), 300–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2022.01.005>
- Grice, H. (1975). Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and semantics* (pp. 41–58, Vol. 3). Academic Press.
- Guest, O. (2024). What makes a good theory, and how do we make a theory good? *Computational Brain & Behavior*, *7*(4), 508–522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-023-00193-2>
- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2021). How computational modeling can force theory building in psychological science. *Association for Psychological Science*, 1–14.
- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2023). On logical inference over brains, behaviour, and artificial neural networks. *Computational Brain & Behavior*, *6*(2), 213–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-022-00166-x>
- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2024, October 9). A metatheory of classical and modern connectionism. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/eaf2z>
- Hawkins, R. D., Frank, M. C., & Goodman, N. D. (2017). Convention-formation in iterated reference games. *Proceedings of the 39th Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*, 6.
- Healey, P. G. T., Mills, G. J., Eshghi, A., & Howes, C. (2018). Running repairs: Coordinating meaning in dialogue. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, *10*(2), 367–388. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12336>
- Hockett, C. F. (1960). The origin of speech. *Scientific American*.
- Holler, J., & Wilkin, K. (2011). Co-speech gesture mimicry in the process of collaborative referring during face-to-face dialogue. *Journal of Nonverbal Behavior*, *35*(2), 133–153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10919-011-0105-6>
- Hutchins, E. (2006). The distributed cognition perspective on human interaction. In *Roots of human sociality*. Routledge.

- Keysar, B., & Bly, B. M. (1999). Swimming against the current: Do idioms reflect conceptual structure? *Journal of Pragmatics*, *31*(12), 1559–1578. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166\(99\)00004-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166(99)00004-1)
- Keysar, B., Lin, S., & Barr, D. J. (2003). Limits on theory of mind use in adults. *Cognition*, *89*(1), 25–41. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(03\)00064-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(03)00064-7)
- Knuth, D. (1968). *The art of computer programming: Sorting and searching*. Addison-Wesley.
- Korzybski, A. (1958). *Science and sanity: An introduction to non-aristotelian systems and general semantics*. Institute of GS. Retrieved April 7, 2017, from https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=KN5gvaDwrGcC&oi=fnd&pg=PR13&dq=korzybski+1933&ots=r14-Bx6n44&sig=t_yLbg5RtGEQHSu06dkx7sDSgfE
- Kuipers, T. A. F. (2000). *From instrumentalism to constructive realism*. Kluwer Academic Publisher.
- Kwisthout, J. (2018). Approximate inference in bayesian networks: Parameterized complexity results. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, *93*, 119–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijar.2017.10.029>
- Levinson, S. C. (1989). A review of relevance. *Journal of Linguistics*, *25*(2), 455–472. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022226700014183>
- Levinson, S. C. (2000). *Presumptive meanings: The theory of generalized conversational implicature*. MIT Press.
- Levinson, S. C. (2006). On the human "interaction engine". In S. C. Levinson & N. J. Enfield (Eds.), *Roots of human sociality: Culture, cognition and interaction* (pp. 39–69). Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003135517-3>
- Levinson, S. C. (2016). Turn-taking in human communication – origins and implications for language processing. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *20*(1), 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.10.010>
- Levinson, S. C., & Holler, J. (2014). The origin of human multi-modal communication. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *369*(1651), 20130302. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0302>
- Macuch Silva, V., Holler, J., Ozyurek, A., & Roberts, S. G. (2020). Multimodality and the origin of a novel communication system in face-to-face interaction. *Royal Society Open Science*, *7*(1), 182056. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.182056>
- Marr, D. (1982). *Vision: A computational investigation into the human representation and processing of visual information*. W.H. Freeman.
- McCarthy, J., & Hayes, P. (1969). Some philosophical problems from the standpoint of artificial intelligence. In D. Michie & B. Meltzer (Eds.), *Machine intelligence 4* (pp. 463–502). Edinburgh University Press.
- Mercier, H., & Sperber, D. (2018, September 24). *The enigma of reason*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674977860>
- Micklos, A., Walker, B., & Fay, N. (2020). Are people sensitive to problems in communication? *Cognitive Science*, *44*(2), e12816. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12816>
- Micklos, A., & Woensdregt, M. (2023, October 18). Cognitive and interactive mechanisms for mutual understanding in conversation. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228613.013.134>
- Mills, G. J. (2014). Dialogue in joint activity: Complementarity, convergence and conventionalization. *New Ideas in Psychology*, *32*, 158–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newideapsych.2013.03.006>
- Morgenstern, L. (1996). The problem with solutions to the frame problem. In K. Ford & Z. Pylyshyn (Eds.), *The robot's dilemma revisited: The frame problem in artificial intelligence*. (pp. 99–133). Ablex Publishing Co., Norwood, New Jersey.

- Newman-Norlund, S. E., Noordzij, M. L., Newman-Norlund, R. D., Volman, I. A. C., de Ruiter, J. P., Hagoort, P., & Toni, I. (2009). Recipient design in tacit communication. *Cognition*, *111*(1), 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2008.12.004>
- Newton, D. P., & Newton, L. D. (1995). Using analogy to help young children understand. *Educational Studies*, *21*(3), 379–393. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305569950210305>
- Nielsen, A. K. S., & Dingemanse, M. (2021). Iconicity in word learning and beyond: A critical review. *Language and Speech*, *64*(1), 52–72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0023830920914339>
- Nölle, J., & Galantucci, B. (2022). Experimental semiotics: Past, present, and future. In *The routledge handbook of semiosis and the brain*. Routledge.
- Özyürek, A. (2014). Hearing and seeing meaning in speech and gesture: Insights from brain and behaviour. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *369*(1651), 20130296. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0296>
- Perniss, P., Thompson, R., & Vigliocco, G. (2010). Iconicity as a general property of language: Evidence from spoken and signed languages. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *1*. Retrieved October 27, 2022, from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2010.00227>
- Perniss, P., & Vigliocco, G. (2014). The bridge of iconicity: From a world of experience to the experience of language. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *369*(1651). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0292>
- Pohlhaus, G. (2012). Relational knowing and epistemic injustice: Toward a theory of willful hermeneutical ignorance. *Hypatia*, *27*(4), 715–735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01222.x>
- Pouw, W., & Fuchs, S. (2022). Origins of vocal-entangled gesture. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *141*, 104836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104836>
- Punselie, S., McLean, B., & Dingemanse, M. (2024). The anatomy of iconicity: Cumulative structural analogies underlie objective and subjective measures of iconicity. *Open Mind*, *8*, 1191–1212. https://doi.org/10.1162/opmi_a_00162
- Rasenberg, M., Özyürek, A., Bögels, S., & Dingemanse, M. (2022). The primacy of multimodal alignment in converging on shared symbols for novel referents. *Discourse Processes*, *59*(3), 209–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163853X.2021.1992235>
- Rasenberg, M., Pouw, W., Özyürek, A., & Dingemanse, M. (2022). The multimodal nature of communicative efficiency in social interaction. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-22883-w>
- Rich, P., de Haan, R., Wareham, T., & van Rooij, I. (2021). How hard is cognitive science? *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, *43*(43). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8cr8x1c4>
- Roberts, F., & Francis, A. L. (2013). Identifying a temporal threshold of tolerance for silent gaps after requests. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, *133*(6), EL471–EL477. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4802900>
- Sacks, H., Schegloff, E. A., & Jefferson, G. (1974). A simplest systematics for the organization of turn-taking for conversation. *Language*, *50*(4), 696–735. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.1974.0010>
- Schegloff, E. A. (1991). Conversation analysis and socially shared cognition. In L. B. Resnick, J. M. Levine, & S. D. Teasley (Eds.), *Perspectives on socially shared cognition* (pp. 150–171). American Psychological Association.
- Schegloff, E. A., Jefferson, G., & Sacks, H. (1977). The preference for self-correction in the organization of repair in conversation. *Language*, *53*(2), 361–382.
- Schelling, T. C. (1958). The strategy of conflict . prospectus for a reorientation of game theory. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, *2*(3), 203–264. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002200275800200301>

- Schelling, T. C. (1961). Experimental games and bargaining theory. *World Politics*, 14(1), 47–68. Retrieved November 18, 2024, from <https://heinonline.org/HOL/P?h=hein.journals/wpot14&i=57>
- Seo, M.-S., & Koshik, I. (2010). A conversation analytic study of gestures that engender repair in ESL conversational tutoring. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 42(8), 2219–2239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2010.01.021>
- Skorstad, J., Gentner, D., & Medin, D. (1988). Abstraction processes during concept learning: A structural view. *Proceedings of the Tenth Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*, 419–425.
- Sperber, D., & Wilson, D. (2001). *Relevance: Communication and cognition* (2nd ed). Blackwell Publishers.
- Steels, L. (2015). *The talking heads experiment: Origins of words and meanings*. Language Science Press. https://doi.org/10.26530/OAPEN_559870
- Stolk, A., Verhagen, L., Schoffelen, J.-M., Oostenveld, R., Blokpoel, M., Hagoort, P., van Rooij, I., & Toni, I. (2013). Neural mechanisms of communicative innovation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(36), 14574–14579. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1303170110>
- Taub, S. F. (2000). Iconicity in american sign language: Concrete and metaphorical applications. *Spatial Cognition and Computation*, 2(1), 31–50. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011440231221>
- van Fraassen, B. (1985). Empiricism in the philosophy of science. In P. Churchland & C. Hooker (Eds.), *Images of science: Essays on realism and empiricism* (p. 245). University of Chicago Press.
- van Rooij, I. (2008). The tractable cognition thesis. *Cognitive Science: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 32(6), 939–984. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03640210801897856>
- van Rooij, I. (2015). How the curse of intractability can be cognitive science’s blessing. *Proceedings of the 37th Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/3p94n>
- van Rooij, I. (2022). Psychological models and their distractors. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1(3), 127–128. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-022-00031-5>
- van Rooij, I., & Baggio, G. (2021). Theory before the test: How to build high-verisimilitude explanatory theories in psychological science. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620970604>
- van Rooij, I., & Blokpoel, M. (2020). Formalizing verbal theories: A tutorial by dialogue. *Social Psychology*, 51(5), 285–298. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-9335/a000428>
- van Rooij, I., Blokpoel, M., Kwisthout, J., & Wareham, T. (2019). *Cognition and intractability: A guide to classical and parameterized complexity analysis*. Cambridge University Press.
- van Rooij, I., Evans, P., Müller, M., Gedge, J., & Wareham, T. (2008). Identifying sources of intractability in cognitive models: An illustration using analogical structure mapping. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 30(30).
- van Rooij, I., Guest, O., Adolfi, F., de Haan, R., Kolokolova, A., & Rich, P. (2024). Reclaiming AI as a theoretical tool for cognitive science. *Computational Brain & Behavior*, 7(4), 616–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-024-00217-5>
- van Rooij, I., Kwisthout, J., Blokpoel, M., Szymanik, J., Wareham, T., & Toni, I. (2011). Intentional communication: Computationally easy or difficult? *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 5(52), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2011.00052>
- van Rooij, I., & Wareham, T. (2007). Parameterized complexity in cognitive modeling: Foundations, applications and opportunities. *The Computer Journal*, 51(3), 385–404. <https://doi.org/10.1093/comjnl/bxm034>

- Van Benthem, J., Ghosh, S., & Verbrugge, R. (Eds.). (2015). *Models of strategic reasoning* (Vol. 8972). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-48540-8>
- van de Braak, L. D., de Haan, R., Dingemanse, M., Toni, I., van Rooij, I., & Blokpoel, M. (2024). Intractability obstacles to explanations of communication. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Cognitive Modeling*, 22.
- van de Braak, L. D., Dingemanse, M., Toni, I., van Rooij, I., & Blokpoel, M. (2021). Computational challenges in explaining communication: How deep the rabbit hole goes. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 43(43). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4pj1g2q8>
- van de Pol, I., van Rooij, I., & Szymanik, J. (2018). Parameterized complexity of theory of mind reasoning in dynamic epistemic logic. *Journal of Logic, Language and Information*, 27(3), 255–294. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10849-018-9268-4>
- Van Huyck, J. B., Battalio, R. C., & Beil, R. O. (1990). Tacit coordination games, strategic uncertainty, and coordination failure. *The American Economic Review*, 80(1), 234–248. Retrieved March 25, 2025, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2006745>
- Ware, C. (1993). The foundations of experimental semiotics: A theory of sensory and conventional representation. *Journal of Visual Languages & Computing*, 4(1), 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvlc.1993.1006>
- Wheatley, T., Boncz, A., Toni, I., & Stolk, A. (2019). Beyond the isolated brain: The promise and challenge of interacting minds. *Neuron*, 103(2), 186–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.05.009>
- Wilson, D., & Sperber, D. (2004). Relevance theory. In *Handbook of pragmatics* (pp. 607–632).
- Winter, B., Woodin, G., & Perlman, M. (n.d.). Defining iconicity for the cognitive sciences. In *Oxford handbook of iconicity in language*. Oxford University Press. Retrieved November 27, 2024, from <https://osf.io/5e3rc>
- Woensdregt, M., Blokpoel, M., van Rooij, I., & Martin, A. E. (2024). Challenges for a computational explanation of flexible linguistic inference. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 46(0).